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OBMD library for LAMMPS

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the open-boundary molecular dynamics (OBMD) method and its implementation within the Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) simulation package. Typically, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are conducted in the canonical ensemble, which maintains a constant number of particles, volume, and temperature. However, many real systems are open and can exchange mass, momentum, and energy with their surroundings. This necessitates the use of the grand-canonical ensemble to perform simulations. The OBMD method makes this possible by allowing particle exchange through the opening of the system's boundaries. To this end, the OBMD method enables imposition of the external boundary conditions defined by the normal component of the momentum flux, where the governing equations of motion in the bulk remain intact.

The implementation of the OBMD method introduces a new fix style called `obmd`, which manages the deletion and insertion of particles, measures the outflow of linear momentum of deleted particles, and applies external forces to particles in the buffer regions, thereby enabling the imposition of the user-defined boundary conditions. The execution of the newly implemented `obmd` extension is invoked by specific methods within the LAMMPS code.

To demonstrate the applicability of the newly implemented `obmd` extension, we performed both equilibrium and non-equilibrium simulations of liquid water using the mesoscopic dissipative particle dynamics (DPD) and simple point charge (SPC) water models. Our findings clearly show that open boundaries do not affect the structural properties of the liquid. Furthermore, we showcased the application of the `obmd` extension as a virtual ultrasound machine and virtual rheometer, emphasizing the significant potential of the OBMD method for biomedical applications.

In addition, we investigated the strong scalability of the DPD fluid in equilibrium using the LAMMPS code with the `obmd` extension enabled. We compared these results to simulations where periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) were utilized. The results demonstrated that the introduction of the `obmd` extension does not significantly affect the strong scaling behavior of the LAMMPS code. We observed excellent scalability up to at least 80 A100 GPUs, which represents approximately one-third of the EuroHPC Vega GPU partition. The observed behavior is crucial for large-scale simulations, ensuring that our methods remain efficient when applied on advanced supercomputing infrastructures.

The appendices to this deliverable include essential resources such as the user guide, programmer's manual, and architectural document, all designed to further support users and developers of the `obmd` extension. The user guide offers step-by-step instructions for compiling LAMMPS with the `obmd` extension and conducting OBMD simulations. The programmer's manual provides insight into the structure and functions of the new header and implementation files, while the architectural document provides details about the communication patterns associated with the newly added `obmd` fix style.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable outlines the **OBMD** method, which opens the system boundaries and allows imposition of the external boundary conditions, while leaving the governing equations of motion in the bulk intact.

It includes a detailed description of the implementation of the **OBMD** method as a newly integrated `obmd` extension within the **LAMMPS** code (version: 7Feb2024).

To demonstrate the versatility of applications enabled by the **OBMD** method, we present and discuss the results obtained by performing equilibrium and nonequilibrium **OBMD** simulations employing **DPD** and **SPC** water model.

Additionally, the deliverable features a user guide and a programmer's manual. The user guide provides comprehensive instructions on compiling **LAMMPS** with the `obmd` extension and conducting **OBMD** simulations with the provided Python script that generates an input script for **LAMMPS**.

The programmer's manual provides information on the structure and functions of the added header and implementation files, which are utilized to execute **OBMD** simulations. The architectural document addresses the communication patterns and key components of the new `obmd` fix style.

1.2 Target audience

This deliverable is aimed (but not limited) to:

- people employing **MD** simulations,
- people using **LAMMPS** **MD** simulation code,
- people who want to exploit **OBMD** method to perform simulations,
- people who want to further extend the **OBMD** method,
- people who want to test scaling of the system.

1.3 Report outline

This deliverable is structured as follows. Sec. 2 provides a detailed description of the **OBMD** method and gives an insight into its implementation within the **LAMMPS** code. The primary focus of Sec. 3 is to illustrate the execution of a simulation timestep and to identify the stages at which the functions of the `obmd` extension are invoked. In Sec. 4, we define the external boundary conditions required for the imposition of a constant normal load, inducing shear flow, or exciting acoustic waves. In the same section, we present and discuss the results obtained from the **OBMD** simulations utilizing the specified boundary conditions. Finally, Sec. 5 examines the impact of the `obmd` extension on the scaling behavior of the **LAMMPS** code.

Additionally, the user guide (Appendix A.1), programmer's manual (Appendix A.2), and architectural document (Appendix A.3) are included at the end of this deliverable, providing further resources for users and developers.

2 Overview of the OBMD method

The MD simulations are usually performed in the canonical (NVT) ensemble, mimicking the experimental conditions of constant temperature (T), volume (V), and number of particles (N). However, many real systems are open; therefore, they exchange the mass, momentum, and energy with the external world. To characterize such systems, the grand-canonical (μ VT) ensemble is used. The latter is specified by the chemical potential (μ), volume (V), and temperature (T). To this end, grand-canonical MD simulations with a fluctuating number of particles are enabled by the OBMD method [1–3], which by opening of the system's boundaries allows for particle exchange. In OBMD, the simulation box is opened in one direction, while PBCs are applied in the remaining ones. The box is divided into three regions, where the central region of interest (ROI) is enclosed by two buffer regions (as depicted in Fig. 1). Buffers

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the OBMD simulation setup.

serve as particle reservoirs, where particles are removed from and inserted into the system. The number of particles in the buffers is maintained by the following feedback algorithm:

$$\Delta N_b = \frac{\delta t}{\tau_b} (\langle N_b \rangle - N_b), \quad (1)$$

where $\langle N_b \rangle$ and N_b are the desired and current numbers of particles inside the buffer, respectively, while τ_b represents the relaxation time of the buffer. When there are more particles in the buffer than $\langle N_b \rangle$, that is, when $\Delta N_b < 0$, the particles need to be deleted from the system. In practice, particles are not deleted immediately, but rather left to diffuse across the outer boundary of the buffer and then deleted. In contrast, new particles are inserted when $\Delta N_b > 0$, implying that there are fewer particles inside the buffer than desired. The insertion of new particles is carried out using the iterative USHER algorithm [4]. The algorithm begins by selecting a random position within the buffer for the particle to be inserted. Then, the potential energy of the particle is calculated relative to all other particles in the buffer. If the calculated potential energy is below a predefined threshold (U^0), the position is accepted and the particle is inserted. On the other hand, if the energy is higher, the position is iteratively corrected according to the following update rule:

$$\mathbf{r}^{n+1} = \mathbf{r}^n + \frac{\mathbf{f}^n}{|\mathbf{f}^n|} \delta s^n. \quad (2)$$

Here, \mathbf{r}^n is the position of the particle at n -th iteration and \mathbf{f}^n is the total force on a given particle in the same iteration step. The displacement δs^n depends on the local potential energy U^n and force magnitude $|\mathbf{f}^n|$. If the computed energy U^n is larger than U_{ovlp} , which is chosen to be a very large energy, representing an overlap position, δs^n is computed using $\delta s^n = \Delta s_{ovlp} = r_\sigma - (4\epsilon/U^n)^{1/2}$. Here, the position of the particle will be translated for a distance r_σ from the center of mass of the overlapped particle. When the calculated energy is lower than U_{ovlp} , δs is determined using $\delta s^n = \min(\Delta s, (U^n - U^0)/|\mathbf{f}^n|)$. The iterative procedure is performed until the computed energy is below the predefined threshold. If this does not succeed within the specified number of steps, the position is rejected, and the insertion is repeated by selecting another random position.

The buffers are also utilized to introduce external boundary conditions, while keeping the equations of motion unchanged. To impose boundary conditions, OBMD employs external forces \mathbf{f}_i^{ext} acting only on particles within buffers, i.e., $\mathbf{f}_i^{ext} = 0$ everywhere else [3]. In addition, in OBMD the total linear momentum is conserved, which directly stems from the Navier-Stokes equation, coming on top of the linear momentum conservation law

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{v})}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}^p. \quad (3)$$

Here, ρ , \mathbf{v} , and \mathbf{J}^p are the fluid density, fluid velocity, and momentum flux tensor, respectively. The latter is expressed as

$$\mathbf{J}^p = \rho \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v} + \Pi, \quad (4)$$

where Π is the stress tensor, given by

$$\Pi = (P + \pi)\mathbf{I} + \bar{\Pi}. \quad (5)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of Eq. 5 is diagonal, where P is the thermodynamic pressure, and $\pi = -\zeta \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}$, i.e., the isotropic stress. The second term is a traceless symmetric tensor, whose components are

$$\bar{\Pi}_{\alpha\beta} = -\eta(\partial_\alpha v_\beta + \partial_\beta v_\alpha - 2\partial_\gamma v_\gamma \delta_{\alpha\beta} D^{-1}). \quad (6)$$

Here, D stands for spatial dimension, while symbols η and ζ denote the shear and bulk viscosity coefficient, respectively.

In OBMD, boundary conditions are defined by the normal component of the momentum flux, i.e., $J^p \cdot \mathbf{n}$, where J^p stands for the already defined momentum flux tensor and \mathbf{n} is the unit vector normal to the interface buffer-ROI (pointing towards the center of the ROI). To determine external forces used to impose the external boundary conditions, the amount of momentum created by such forces over one timestep (δt) should be evaluated, and the result equated to the desired amount of momentum that needs to be added to or extracted from the system. By reformulating the momentum flux balance equation for the OBMD boundary of the surface A ,

$$J^p \cdot \mathbf{n} A \delta t = \sum_{i \in B} \mathbf{f}_i^{ext} \delta t + \sum_{i'} \Delta(m_{i'} \mathbf{v}_{i'}), \quad (7)$$

we arrive at the expression for the total external force \mathbf{F}^{ext} :

$$\mathbf{F}^{ext} = \sum_{i \in B} \mathbf{f}_i^{ext} = A \left(J^p \cdot \mathbf{n} - \frac{\sum_{i' \in B} \Delta(m_{i'} \mathbf{v}_{i'})}{A \delta t} \right). \quad (8)$$

Indices i and i' run over all the particles in the buffers and over all particles that have been inserted into or deleted from the system in the last timestep, respectively. Accordingly, the momentum change is given by $\Delta(m_{i'} \mathbf{v}_{i'}) = \pm m_{i'} \mathbf{v}_{i'}$ if the particle i' is inserted (+) or deleted (-), where $m_{i'}$ and $\mathbf{v}_{i'}$ represent the mass and velocity of the particle i' , respectively. Ultimately, the total external force \mathbf{F}^{ext} is distributed among the particles in the buffer using

$$\mathbf{f}_i^{ext} = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{r}_i) \mathbf{F}^{ext}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{r}_i)$ is a weighting function, generally in tensorial form, allowing distribution of normal and tangential forces (see Fig. 2) [1, 3].

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the weighting functions g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} that are used to distribute normal and tangential forces, respectively.

3 Implementation of OBMD method in LAMMPS

In this section, we describe how the OBMD method (presented in Sec. 2) is implemented in the LAMMPS code by closely inspecting:

- the newly added OBMD package (see Fig. 3), which includes the new obmd extension for LAMMPS simulation package,
- deletion and insertion of particles,
- measurement of the outflow of the linear momentum of particles that have diffused across the outer boundary of the buffers,
- imposition of the external boundary conditions using external force.

Figure 3: Directory tree showing the contents of the OBMD package and the newly added pair style of the KOKKOS package.

The execution of the obmd extension within a timestep is triggered by the `pre_exchange()` and `post_force()` methods (see Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). In the `pre_exchange()` method, particles are inserted or deleted before rebuilding the neighbor list. In the `pre_exchanged()` method, the `try_deleting()` member function is called first. Here, particles that have left the outer boundary of the buffers are marked for deletion. In the process of deletion, a loop is made over

Figure 4: Schematic illustration of the timestep and functions called in the `pre_exchange()` method. Blue colored rectangle contains the newly implemented function (blue text) and variables defined (black text) in the obmd extension. To increase readability, comments are also provided (gray text).

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of the timestep and functions called in the `post_force()` method. Same color coding is used as in Fig. 4.

all the particles, but then only those that are marked get deleted, and the sum of their (outgoing) linear momentum is computed. The `try_deleting()` member function returns the `vnew` array of length three, carrying information about the computed linear momentum in the x -, y -, and z -direction, respectively. The number of particles to be inserted into the system is calculated according to eq. 1 and stored in variable `ninsert`. Then a call to the `try_inserting()` member function is made. As described in Sec. 2, the initial position within the buffer region is randomly selected for the particle that needs to be inserted. Then, its energy is computed with respect to the other particles in the buffer region by making a call to the `usher()` member function. In the case of charged particles, the potential energy is computed using the reaction field (rf) method by calling the `energy_charged_obmd()` method. On the other hand, when non-charged particles are inserted, their energy is calculated by calling the `single()` method of the selected potential in the `energy()` member function. Both member functions, i.e., `energy_charged_obmd()` and `energy()`, return the potential energy of the particle that is stored in variable `entmp`. If the computed energy is too high (meaning the particles are too close or overlap), the position is iteratively corrected using eq. 2. The procedure is repeated until the energy falls below a predefined threshold. However, if the insertion is not successful within a specified number of steps, the position is rejected and the insertion process is repeated by selecting another random position. At the moment, particles are inserted having a zero velocity, and thus the measured (ingoing) linear momentum is zero. In addition, the insertion procedure can be performed using `near`, which is adopted from the already existing routine in the `deposit` fix style. The insertion procedure is followed by the second call to the `try_deleting()` member function, checking for particles that have left the open boundary and deleting them if they have. Having performed particle deletion and insertion, and measured the (outgoing) linear momentum, `momentumForce` can be determined. The `momentumForce` represents an array of length three and carries information about the external boundary condition to be applied in the x -, y -, and z -direction, respectively. It is evaluated using eq. 8. The same applies to the `shearForce`, which also represents an array of length three and holds information about the shear stress to be applied. The latter is used when simulations of a shear flow are performed. The workflow explained above is schematically depicted in Fig. 4.

To tackle electrostatic interactions of charged particles beyond the cutoff in the OBMD simulations, we implemented a new custom pair potential `lj/cut/rf` (see Fig. 5). The latter computes the Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential and treats electrostatics using the rf method [5]. The `pair_style lj/cut/rf` can be performed on graphical processing unit (GPU) by selecting `pair_style lj/cut/rf/kk`, which is added to the KOKKOS package (see Fig. 3) and takes the same arguments as the `lj/cut/rf` pair style.

External forces are accounted after bonded and non-bonded forces have been applied by invoking the `post_force()` method. Within this method, the `reg_force()` member function is called to distribute in the `pre_exchange()` method computed total external force, i.e., `momentumForce`, in the normal direction, while distribution of the total external force acting in tangential direction, i.e., `shear_force`, is performed by calling the `reg_perp_force()`. The distribution of the total external force follows eq. 9, and the resulting external force that acts on a particle is added to the force (vector) of each particle. The workflow discussed above is schematically depicted in Fig. 5.

For more details on the implementation, we refer the reader to the documents accompanying this deliverable and to the OBMD [GitHub repository](#). In the next section, we show the results obtained by performing equilibrium and nonequilibrium OBMD simulations with non-charged and charged particles using the newly implemented obmd extension.

4 OBMD simulations of liquid water employing DPD and SPC water models

To demonstrate the applicability of the obmd extension, we simulated liquid water described using the mesoscopic DPD water model [6] and the SPC water model [7]. To correctly reproduce the hydrodynamics in our simulations, we applied the DPD thermostat [8–12], which allows for the conservation of linear momentum and thus recovers the Navier-Stokes equations in the continuum limit. The latter is crucial when performing OBMD simulations. In addition, all simulations have been and should be performed using reduced units to avoid errors in the calculation of the external force and unexpected behavior of the system when the latter is applied.

To simulate the system under a constant normal load (p) applied from both sides of the simulation domain in the open direction, the momentum flux tensor of the external force (eq. 8) reads as

$$\mathbf{J}A \cdot \mathbf{n} = p_{xx}A\mathbf{n}, \quad (10)$$

where $p_{xx} = p$ [1]. By introducing a sinusoidal disturbance and rewriting the above momentum flux equation into

$$\mathbf{J}A \cdot \mathbf{n} = p_{xx}A\mathbf{n} + \Delta p \sin(2\pi\nu t)A\mathbf{n}, \quad (11)$$

an acoustic wave can be excited [13, 14]. Here, Δp , ν , and t are the amplitude of the excited acoustic wave, frequency, and time, respectively. The oscillatory disturbance is imposed only on one of the buffers, while on the other one only the constant normal load (p) is applied (eq. 10). Using OBMD, we have also performed simulations of a shear flow by adding a term to eq. 10 that applies equally opposite forces to the buffers [15]:

$$\mathbf{J}A \cdot \mathbf{n} = p_{xx}A\mathbf{n} + p_{xy}A\mathbf{t}, \quad (12)$$

where p_{xy} and \mathbf{t} represent the shear stress and unit vector that points in the direction of the shear flow, respectively. The latter is also perpendicular to the unit vector \mathbf{n} , which points towards the center of the simulation box (or ROI).

4.1 DPD water model

In our setup, one DPD particle represented 8 water molecules [6, 16], where units of length, time, mass, and energy were set to $U_L = 0.893$ nm, $U_T = 6.83$ ps, $U_M = 2.39 \cdot 10^{-25}$ kg, and $U_E = k_B T$, respectively. The density was set to $\rho = 3.0 U_L^{-3}$ and equilibrium pressure was determined using the DPD equation of state (EOS) [17]. The latter can also be estimated by conducting equilibrium NVT simulations at a chosen density and monitoring the pressure to which the system relaxes.

The results computed from the equilibrium OBMD simulation with the pressure set to $p_{xx} = 188.0 U_E U_L^{-3}$ are given in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7.

The number density profile depicted in Fig. 6 is flat in the ROI and at the desired density, indicating that there are no spurious effects introduced by open boundaries. Indeed, the density in buffers decreases, but this is not expected to have an impact on the pressure imposed onto the ROI, as the density profile at the boundary buffer-ROI is flat. In

Figure 6: Number density profile along the open direction of the simulation box. The desired density of the DPD water is depicted using the black dotted line and is equal to $\rho = 3.0 U_L^{-3}$. The two orange dotted lines indicate boundaries buffer-ROI.

addition, we have also inspected whether the introduction of open boundaries affects the structural properties of the

Figure 7: RDF for the DPD water. Black line and dots correspond to the RDF computed from NVT simulation, while blue line and dots depict the RDF computed from the OBMD simulations.

simulated system by computing the radial distribution function (RDF) of the DPD water in the ROI and compared it to the one calculated from the NVT simulation. The comparison in Fig. 7 shows that they are in perfect agreement. This clearly indicates that the structural properties of the system are preserved. Linear momentum (buffer + ROI) was also observed to be conserved.

Having demonstrated that open boundaries do not affect structural properties of the simulated liquid and do not introduce artifacts in the OBMD simulations, we decided to check how OBMD performs when an acoustic wave is introduced (eq. 11). The results depicted in Fig. 8 illustrate that the calculated density variation through the simulation box is in good agreement with the analytical prediction described by

$$\rho = \rho_0 + \Delta\rho \sin(\omega t - kx + \varphi)e^{-\alpha x}, \quad (13)$$

where parameters α , k , ω , x , and ϕ represent the attenuation coefficient, wave number, angular frequency ($\omega = 2\pi\nu$), distance, and phase shift, respectively, and are known inputs at time t . The Fig. 8 shows that acoustic waves can be successfully simulated using the obmd extension as a virtual ultrasound machine. The next step is to probe the obmd extension as a virtual rheometer. As can be seen in Fig. 9, using the obmd extension to introduce two oppositely equal forces along the y -axis in the buffers (eq. 12), a shear flow can also be induced in the system.

Figure 8: Computed density variation through the ROI for a simulated acoustic wave with frequency of $1.84 U_T^{-1}$ and $\Delta p = 0.5 p_{xx}$ at times $t = 0$ (left panel), $t \approx t_0/2$ (middle panel), and $t = t_0$ (right panel). The analytical solution is shown using the blue solid line, while black dots represent simulation data.

The presented results demonstrate that the obmd extension performs well when simulating non-charged particles. To investigate its performance when charged particles are present in the system, we performed additional OBMD simulations using the SPC water model and repeated the calculations.

Figure 9: Calculated velocity profile v_y along the open direction of the simulation box at $p_{xy} = 0.8 U_E U_L^{-3}$. The ROI is sandwiched between the two black dotted lines.

4.2 SPC water model

Employing the SPC water model [7], the units of length, time, mass, and energy were set to $U_L = 0.3166$ nm, $U_T = 1.5707$ ps, $U_M = 15.9994$ a.m.u., and $U_E = 0.6500$ kJ mol $^{-1}$, respectively. The density was set to $\rho = 998$ kg m $^{-3}$. The geometry of the water molecules was constrained using SHAKE [18]. Intermolecular interactions were described using the LJ potential and the rf method was used to treat electrostatic interactions beyond the cutoff, where the electric permittivity was set to 80. The cutoff distance of non-bonded interactions was fixed at 0.9 nm.

Figure 10: Mass density profile along the open direction of the simulation box. The desired density of the SPC water is depicted using the black dotted line and is equal to $\rho = 1.2 U_M U_L^{-3}$. The two orange dotted lines indicate the boundaries buffer-ROI.

Inspection of the results obtained showed that, also in this case, opening the system's boundaries did not introduce instabilities (see Fig. 10). Furthermore, the structure of the fluid also remained unaffected (see Fig. 11), as the calculated RDF for oxygen-oxygen, oxygen-hydrogen, and hydrogen-hydrogen were in agreement with those reported in the literature [19].

Similarly to before, an acoustic wave with frequency of $0.21 U_T^{-1}$ and $\Delta p = 2.0 p_{xx}$ was excited in the water described by the SPC model using the obmd extension. Again, the calculated density variation through ROI was in perfect agreement with the analytical solution given by eq. 13 (see Fig. 12). Furthermore, a linear velocity profile through the ROI was obtained (see Fig. 13), when shear flow was imposed into the ROI (eq. 12).

The presented results show that the newly implemented obmd extension for LAMMPS not only allows equilibrium OBMD simulations of non-charged and charged particles, but can also be utilized to inspect the system behavior after subjecting it to different sources of mechanical stress. This can provide computational insight into the effect of mechanical stress on macromolecules and may be of particular interest in the field of biomedicine, as well as in the optimization and development of bioprocessing equipment.

Figure 11: RDFs for the SPC water. Black line and dots correspond to RDF calculated from the NVT simulation, while blue line and dots depict RDF computed from OBMD simulations. In both cases, the rf method was used to describe electrostatic interactions beyond the cutoff. Black dotted lines denote distances and corresponding values of $g(r)$ reported in the literature for the SPC water.

Figure 12: Computed density variation through the ROI for simulated acoustic wave with frequency of $0.21 U_T^{-1}$ and $\Delta p = 2.0 p_{xx}$ at times $t = 1/6 t_0$ (left panel), $t \approx 1/3 t_0$ (middle panel), and $t = t_0$ (right panel). The analytical solution is shown using the blue solid line, while black dots represent simulation data.

Figure 13: Calculated velocity profile v_y along the open direction of the simulation box at $p_{xy} = 2.0 U_E U_L^{-3}$. The ROI is located between the two black dotted lines.

5 Scaling study

In this section, we investigate whether the `obmd` extension affects the scaling behavior of the `LAMMPS` code.

Figure 14: Strong scalability study performed using the DPD fluid. The dashed lines indicate results obtained when the PBCs are applied, while solid lines show data collected using the `obmd` extension.

To this end, we have conducted a strong scalability study of the DPD fluid in equilibrium using the `obmd` extension and compared it with the NVT simulations, where PBCs were applied. The results obtained demonstrate that the strong scalability behavior of the `LAMMPS` code is not greatly affected by the introduction of the `obmd` extension. In addition, we observed an excellent strong scalability behavior up to at least 80 A100 GPUs, which is about one-third of the EuroHPC Vega GPU partition. To put this into perspective, each A100 GPU delivers approximately 10 TFlops in double precision and 20 TFlops in single precision. This means that the 80 GPU workload we tested was running on hardware with raw compute capabilities between 0.75 and 1.5 Petaflops, highlighting the immense computational power used. Such scalability is crucial for large-scale simulations, as it ensures that our methods remain efficient even when applied on advanced supercomputing infrastructures.

6 Conclusion and perspectives

In conclusion, this deliverable presented a comprehensive overview of the OBMD method and its integration into the LAMMPS code (version 7 Feb 2024). The newly added obmd extension will allow performing OBMD simulations in and out-of-equilibrium, as demonstrated in this deliverable. At the same time, we showed that scalability behavior of the LAMMPS code is not greatly affected by the introduction of the presented obmd extension.

We aim to integrate the presented obmd extension into the official LAMMPS release, upon successful completion of Tasks 3.2 and 4.4. The latter are specifically designed to enhance the functionality of the OBMD method. Prior to this integration, we will deploy our builds and example scripts to dev.eessi.io, i.e., the development repository of EESSI. This will make it easier to test development versions of our LAMMPS code extensions on different system architectures, where `dev.eessi.io CernVM-FS` is available.

A Appendices

The following appendices specific versions of the documents that are extracted from the [OBMD GitHub repository](#) (the latest versions can be found there).

A.1 OBMD User Guide

This document serves as a guide for users and developers working with the `obmd` extension in LAMMPS. Therefore, **general knowledge about LAMMPS and molecular dynamics simulations is assumed**. Additionally, basic familiarity with compiling and running C++ code is expected.

To perform open-boundary molecular dynamics (OBMD) simulations using the `obmd` extension, we provide a **Python script** named `input.py`, which generates `in.simulation` input script for LAMMPS. LAMMPS is then started with this input as a parameter, for example,

```
lmp_mpi -in in.simulation
```

The script `input.py` is located [here](#).

INITIALIZATION SETTINGS

A code snippet of the **function** in the `input.py` Python script, which writes the input script for the LAMMPS OBMD simulation of a **DPD fluid**, is given and explained below.

First, the generated output file name, which serves as the input for LAMMPS (`in_file`), is set. The default value is `in.simulation`. Next, the `write_in(in_file)` function is defined, taking the name of the input file to be created as an argument. Using an f-string, the block of code that forms the input script is stored in `content_4in`. Finally, the content is written to a file using `file_to_write.write(content_4in)`.

```
in_file = "in.simulation"

# ----- #
def write_in(in_file):
    file_to_write = open(in_file, 'w')

    content_4in = f"""
# ----- Variables Section -----
units          lj
boundary       f p p
atom_style     atomic
comm_modify    vel yes
newton         on

region         leftB block {xlo} {buffer_size} {ylo} {yhi} {zlo} {zhi}
region         rightB block {xhi-buffer_size} {xhi} {ylo} {yhi} {zlo} {zhi}
region         leftshear block {xlo} {shear_size} {ylo} {yhi} {zlo} {zhi}
region         rightshear block {xhi-shear_size} {xhi} {ylo} {yhi} {zlo} {zhi}
region         leftBin block {offset} {buffer_size-offset} {offset} {yhi-offset} {offset} {zhi-
offset}
region         rightBin block {xhi-buffer_size+offset} {xhi-offset} {offset} {yhi-offset}
{offset}{zhi-offset}
region         roi block {buffer_size} {xhi-buffer_size} {ylo} {yhi} {zlo} {zhi}

```

OBMD simulations should be performed using **reduced units** (`units lj`) to avoid errors in the calculation of the external force and the style of boundaries (`boundary`) for the global simulation box in each dimension should be set to `f p p`. The latter applies the same style to the lower and upper sides of the simulation box, i.e., in the case of OBMD simulations, the non-periodic style `f` is applied in the x -direction, while the box is periodic in y - and z -directions by choosing the periodic style `p`.

Following is the explanation of the inputs.

- `atom_style` value
The style of atoms in the system. The `obmd` extension was tested using `atomic`, `full`, and `molecular atom`

styles.

When performing OBMD simulations, a **momentum-conserving thermostat** should be applied. Usually, the **DPD thermostat** is used, where velocities should be communicated between neighboring processors and stored as properties of ghost atoms using `comm_modify vel yes`. Importantly, Newton's third law for pairwise and bonded interactions should be enabled via `newton on`.

One should also define geometric regions. Here, **6 regions** (namely `leftB`, `rightB`, `leftshear`, `rightshear`, `leftBin`, and `rightBin`) must be specified. All regions must be defined using the following format: `xlo xhi ylo yhi zlo zhi` (for instructions on `block style`, readers are referred to the [LAMMPS documentation](#)).

- `leftB` block args
Region defining the **left buffer**, where `Region-ID = leftB`. `buffer_size` is the length of the buffer region, `xlo`, `ylo`, and `zlo` are the lower bounds of the simulation box in the x -, y -, and z -direction, respectively, while `xhi`, `yhi`, and `zhi` are the upper bounds.
- `rightB` block args
Region defining the **right buffer**, where `Region-ID = rightB`.
- `leftshear` block args
Region defining **part of the left buffer where shear forces are applied**. Here, `Region-ID = leftshear`. `shear_size` is the length of the region where shear flow is imposed. If only normal pressure forces are applied, e.g., in the case of equilibrium simulations, `shear_size`, `xlo`, `xhi`, `ylo`, `yhi`, `zlo`, and `zhi` should be set to 0.0.
- `rightshear` block args
Region defining **part of the right buffer where shear forces are applied**. Here, `Region-ID = rightshear`. If only normal pressure forces are applied, e.g., in the case of equilibrium simulations, `shear_size`, `xlo`, `xhi`, `ylo`, `yhi`, `zlo`, and `zhi` should be set to 0.0.
- `leftBin` block args
Region defining **part of the left buffer where new particles are inserted**. Here, `Region-ID = leftBin`. `offset` is the value used to narrow the insertion region.
- `rightBin` block args
Region defining **part of the right buffer where new particles are inserted**. Here, `Region-ID = rightBin`.

SIMULATION SETTINGS AND SYSTEM DEFINITION

```
# ----- Interaction Section -----
pair_style      dpd {temp} {rc} {seed_dpd}

# ----- Atom Definition Section -----
read_data      dpd_8map_obmd.data

# ----- Settings Section -----
pair_coeff      * * {aij} {gamma_dpd} {rc}

neighbor       {skin} bin
neigh_modify   delay 0 every 1

timestep       {dt}

fix            1 all nve
```

- `pair_style dpd` is used to perform simulations employing DPD force field. According to the [LAMMPS documentation](#) it takes temperature (`temp`), cutoff of the interaction (`rc`), and seed (`seed_dpd`) as input parameters. Alongside, the following coefficients (`pair_coeff`) must be given:
 - interaction parameter between atoms i and j (`aij`)
 - friction parameter (`gamma_dpd`)
 - cutoff of the interaction (`rc`)

- `read_data` is used to read a **pre-equilibrated configuration** of the DPD fluid given in the `dpd_8map_obmd.data` file. The latter contains information about the positions of the atoms in **reduced units**. It is important that the position of the atoms do not exceed x_{lo} or x_{hi} of the simulation box; if so, they should be manually "deleted" before conducting the OBMD simulations.

```
fix          2 all obmd {ntype} {nfreq} {seed} {pxx} {pxy} {pxz} {dpxx} {freq} {alpha} {tau}
{nbuf} region1 leftB region2 rightB region3 leftshear region4 rightshear region5 leftBin region6
rightBin buffersize {buffer_size} gfac {gfac} stepparallel {step_parallel} stepperp {step_perp}
maxattempt {maxattempt} usher {usher_flag} {etarget} {ds0} {dtheta0} {uovlp} {dsolvp} {eps}
{nattempt} charged {charge_flag}
```

The above `fix` **invokes** the newly added `obmd` extension in LAMMPS. The associated parameters are given as follows:

- `FIX_ID`
Unique user-assigned name for the fix. Here, `FIX_ID = 2` .
- `GROUP_ID`
ID of the group of atoms to which `fix obmd` is applied. The group used here must already exist. Here, `GROUP_ID = all` .
- `FIX_STYLE`
Name of a `fix` style to be used. In the case of OBMD simulations, one must choose `obmd` .
- `ntype`
Type of inserted particles. Commonly, the `ntype` is chosen to correspond to the type of particles that are part of the `GROUP_ID` group, while for molecules, it should be set to 0.
- `nfreq`
Specifies the number of timesteps after which the `fix obmd` is executed. Typically it set to 1, meaning that the `obmd` extension is invoked at every timestep.
- `seed`
A random number used to generate the initial position of newly inserted particles.
- `pxx`
Pressure applied onto the buffer regions. It represents the **equilibrium pressure of a fluid** and can be derived from the equation of state, or obtained from an NVT simulation by monitoring the pressure to which the system relaxes. Can be provided as a real constant number or as a variable using `v_pxx` .
- `pxy`
Shear stress with forces along the y -axis. It can be given as a real constant number or as a variable using `v_pxy` .
- `pxz`
Shear stress with forces along the z -direction. It can be given as a real constant number or as a variable using `v_pxz` .
- `dpxx value`
Pressure amplitude added to the variable `pxx` and applied only onto the left buffer. It can be utilized to simulate a mechanical pressure wave with a frequency `freq` and can be provided as a real constant number or as a variable using `v_dpxx` .
- `freq`
Frequency of the mechanical pressure wave (if excited, otherwise should be set to 0.0). It can be given as a real constant number or as a variable using `v_freq` .
- `alpha`
Parameter to (further) reduce the desired number of particles in the buffers.
- `tau`
Characteristic relaxation time of the buffers.
- `nbuf`
Desired number of particles in the buffer. It can be computed using $nbuf = N * l_b / l_x$, where N is the total number of particles in the simulation box, l_b is the buffer length, and l_x is the length of the simulation box.

- `region1` value
Region ID of the left buffer, where normal forces are applied. Here, region ID is `value = leftB`.
- `region2` value
Region ID of the right buffer, where normal forces are applied. Here, region ID is `value = rightB`.
- `region3` value
Region ID of the left buffer, where tangential shear forces are applied. Here, region ID is `value = leftshear`.
- `region4` value
Region ID of the right buffer, where tangential shear forces are applied. Here, `value = rightshear`.
- `region5` value
Region ID of the left buffer, where new particles will be inserted. Here, `value = leftBin`.
- `region6` value
Region ID of the right buffer, where new particles will be inserted. Here, `value = rightBin`.
- `buffer_size` value
Length of the buffer region. Here, `value = buffer_size`.
- `gfac` value
Smoothing length. Its value must be between 0.0 and 1.0. Here, `value = gfac`.
- `stepparallel` value
Weighting function used to distribute the total external force acting in **normal direction**. For now only **"smooth" weighting function is implemented** and `value = 1` must be used. Here, `value = step_parallel = 1`.
- `stepperp` value
Weighting function used to distribute the total external force acting in **tangential direction**. For now only **Heaviside step weighting function is implemented** and `value = 0` must be used. Here, `value = step_perp = 0`.
- `maxattempt` value
The maximum number of attempts to perform the insertion by calling the `try_inserting()` member function. Here, `value = max_attempt`. If `maxattempt` value is not given, the default value is set to 1.
- `usher options` Insertion algorithm, where the `options` are:
 - `usher_flag`
`usher_flag` must be set to 1 if one aims to employ the USHER insertion algorithm.
 - `etarget`
Target energy of the newly inserted particle.
 - `ds0`
Displacement step used by the USHER algorithm, which should be small but not too small compared to the interaction range.
 - `dtheta0`
Angular steps used when inserting a molecule.
 - `uovlp`
Very large energy characterizing the overlap position, which is commonly set to 10000.
 - `dsolvp`
Parameter set to the value of the first RDF maximum.
 - `eps`
Parameter used in case of overlaps.
 - `nattempt`
Maximum number of iterations performed by the USHER algorithm, which is typically set to 40.

SIMULATION EXECUTION

```
# ----- Compute Section -----
#
# ----- Output Section -----
run          {steps}
```

```

"""
file_to_write.write(content_4in)
file_to_write.close()

# ----- #

# write input script
if __name__ == "__main__":
    write_in(in_file)
    print(f"file {in_file} is written")

```

The `run` option is used to execute the simulation, where `steps` represent the number of simulation steps to be performed. Finally, the `in.simulation` is written using `file_to_write.write(content_4in)`.

COMBINED INPUT SCRIPT TO RUN OBMD SIMULATIONS USING LAMMPS

Below are example values to generate a file for the OBMD simulation.

```

# ----- Variables Section -----
units          lj
boundary       f p p
atom_style     atomic
comm_modify    vel yes
newton         on

region         leftB block 0.0 5.0391 0.0 11.198 0.0 11.198
region         rightB block 28.5549 33.594 0.0 11.198 0.0 11.198
region         leftshear block 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
region         rightshear block 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
region         leftBin block 0.0 5.0391 0.0 11.198 0.0 11.198
region         rightBin block 28.5549 33.594 0.0 11.198 0.0 11.198
region         roi block 5.0391 28.5549 0.0 11.198 0.0 11.198

# ----- Interaction Section -----
pair_style     dpd 1.0 1.0 2616

# ----- Atom Definition Section -----
read_data     dpd_8map_obmd.data

# ----- Settings Section -----
pair_coeff     * * 209.6 4.5 1.0

neighbor      0.4 bin
neigh_modify  delay 0 every 1

timestep      0.001464

fix          1 all nve
fix          2 all obmd 1 1 6111 188.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.7 0.005 1327 &
            region1 leftB region2 rightB region3 leftshear &
            region4 rightshear region5 leftBin region6 rightBin &
            buffersize 5.0391 gfac 0.25 stepparallel 0 stepperp 1 &
            maxattempt 1 usher 1 31.03 1.0 0.02 10000 1.5 1.0 40 charged 0

# ----- Compute Section -----

#

# ----- Output Section -----
run          2000000

```

If you are using `fix obmd`, please **cite the following articles**:

- R. Delgado-Buscalioni, J. Sablić, and M. Praprotnik, *Eur. Phys. J. Special Topics* **224**, 2331-2349 (2015).
- R. Delgado-Buscalioni, K. Kremer, and M. Praprotnik, *J. Chem. Phys.* **128**, 114110 (2008).
- J. Sablić, M. Praprotnik, and R. Delgado-Buscalioni, *Soft Matter* **12**, 2416-2439 (2016).
- L. Delle Site and M. Praprotnik, *Phys. Rep.* **693**, 1-56 (2017).
- P. Papež and M. Praprotnik, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **18**, 1227-1240 (2022).
- R. Delgado-Buscalioni and P. V. Coveney, *J. Chem. Phys.* **119**, 978-987 (2003).

A.2 OBMD Programmers Manual

In the Programmer's manual, instructions on how to compile LAMMPS (**version 7 Feb 2024**) with the `obmd` extension are provided, along with explanation of the structure, classes, and function of the added `lj/cut/xf` pair style. The code introduced below can be downloaded [here](#).

OBMD PACKAGE

The OBMD package is added to the LAMMPS code as a subdirectory with the package name in capital letters. **OBMD package represents the extension that allows grand-canonical simulations in and out-of-equilibrium using particles.** To this end, it implements routines that take care of the deletion and insertion of particles, as well as computation and distribution of external forces, used to impose user-defined external boundary conditions (e.g., constant normal load, shear flow, mechanical pressure wave).

Build LAMMPS using CMake with OBMD extension enabled

To perform OBMD simulations, LAMMPS code needs to be compiled with the OBMD package enabled. Instructions on how to compile LAMMPS can be found [here](#), while the OBMD package can be included using `-D PKG_OBMD=on` when compiling.

```
#!/bin/sh

mkdir -p build_mpi

cd build_mpi

cmake ../cmake \
-D PKG_OBMD=on

make -j 12
```

Additions of the OBMD package

- `src/OBMD`
- `fix_obmd`

FIX STYLE `obmd`

In this section, we explain the `obmd` extension, which is implemented as a new **fix style** within the `FixObmdMerged` class and is used for conducting OBMD simulations both in and out-of-equilibrium. **This fix manages the deletion and insertion of particles while concurrently monitoring the outgoing and incoming linear momentum of both deleted and newly inserted particles**, as implemented in the `fix_obmd_merged.cpp` and its corresponding `fix_obmd_merged.h` header file. Accurately measuring the outgoing and ingoing linear momentum is essential for **imposing the external boundary conditions through external forces**, which is also performed by the `obmd` fix style.

The LAMMPS input syntax is as follows:

```
fix FIX_ID GROUP_ID obmd ntype nfreq seed pxx pxy pxz dpxx freq alpha tau nbuf keyword value
```

The `FIX_ID` serves as the unique identifier for the fix, while `GROUP_ID` specifies the ID of the group to which the fix will be applied. The name of the `obmd` fix style is followed by **11 essential parameters** that are required for its execution.

Namely:

- `ntype`
Atom type to assign to the newly inserted particles (offset when molecule is to be inserted).

- `nfreq`
Specifies the number of timesteps after which the fix is executed.
- `seed`
A random number (positive integer).
- `pxx`
Pressure (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `pxy`
Shear stress with forces acting along y -axis (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `pxz`
Shear stress with forces acting along z -axis (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `dpxx`
Pressure amplitude (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `freq`
Frequency (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `alpha`
Parameter to (further) reduce the desired number of particles in the buffers (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `tau`
Relaxation time of the buffers (real constant number or equal style variable).
- `nbuf`
Desired number of particles in the buffer (real constant number or equal style variable).

Additionally, there are several (optional) parameters (`keyword value`) that can be included to optimize the performance, execution, and various factors within the simulation.

Keyword:

- `region1 value`
Region ID of the left buffer, where **normal forces** are applied.
- `region2 value`
Region ID of the right buffer, where **normal forces** are applied.
- `region3 value`
Region ID of the left buffer, where **tangential shear forces** are applied.
- `region4 value`
Region ID of the right buffer, where **tangential shear forces** are applied.
- `region5 value`
Region ID of the left buffer, where new particles will be inserted.
- `region6 value`
Region ID of the right buffer, where new particles will be inserted.
- `buffersize value`
Length of the buffer region.
- `gfac value`
Smoothing length (value between 0.0 and 1.0).
- `stepparallel value`
Weighting function used to distribute the total external force acting in **normal direction**. `value = 1` represents the "smooth" weighting function.
- `stepperp value`
Weighting function used to distribute the total external force acting in **tangential direction**. `value = 0` represents the Heaviside step weighting function.
- `maxattempt value`
The maximum number of attempts to perform the insertion by calling the `try_inserting()` member function.
- `usher value`
To select `usher` as the insertion algorithm, the `value` should be set to 1, and followed by the parameters below.

- `etarget`
Target energy of the newly inserted particle.
- `ds0`
Displacement step used by the USHER algorithm.
- `dtheta0`
Angular step used when inserting a molecule.
- `uovlp`
Very large energy characterizing the overlap position.
- `dsolvp`
Parameter set to the value of the first RDF maximum.
- `eps`
Parameter used in case of overlaps.
- `nattempt`
Maximum number of iterations performed by the USHER algorithm.
- `charged value`
To simulate **charged** particles, the `value` should be set to 1, otherwise to 0.
- `mol value`
To insert a molecule, the `value` should contain information about molecular template and the number of particles that need to be inserted. For more details, readers are referred to the [LAMMPS documentation](#).

Several other options are adopted from the LAMMPS code:

- `molfrac`
- `rigid`
- `shake`
- `global`
- `local`
- `near`
Represents the insertion algorithm. It is not possible to select both `near` and `usher` at the same time.
- `rate`
- `vx`
- `vy`
- `vz`
- `orient`
- `units`
- `gaussian`
- `target`

and we recommend that readers refer to the [LAMMPS documentation](#) for instructions on how to use them.

HEADER FILE

The first segment of the header file includes a copyright and license statement and attribution statement with a description of the code base and a brief description of the modifications and adjustments made.

```
/* -*- c++ -*- -----
LAMMPS - Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator
http://lammps.sandia.gov, Sandia National Laboratories
Steve Plimpton, sjplimp@sandia.gov

Copyright (2003) Sandia Corporation. Under the terms of Contract
DE-AC04-94AL85000 with Sandia Corporation, the U.S. Government retains
certain rights in this software. This software is distributed under
the GNU General Public License.
```

```

Attribution:
- Original code by Sandia Corporation.
- OBMD extension uses portions of code derived from evaporate and deposit fix style:
https://docs.lammps.org/fix_evaporate.html
https://docs.lammps.org/fix_deposit.html

```

```

See the README file in the top-level LAMMPS directory.
----- */

```

The new fix style is registered with LAMMPS. The name of the fix is `obmd` and `FixObmdMerged` is the name of the class that implements it.

```

#ifdef FIX_CLASS
// clang-format off
FixStyle(obmd, FixObmdMerged)
// clang-format on
#else

// Content

#endif

```

The `// Content` part of the header file contains the complete definition of the `FixObmdMerged` class, including essential `setmask()` method. This method specifies functions that are invoked during the timestep.

```

#ifndef LMP_FIX_OBMD_MERGED_H
#define LMP_FIX_OBMD_MERGED_H

#include "fix.h"

namespace LAMMPS_NS {
class FixObmdMerged : public Fix {
public:
  FixObmdMerged(class LAMMPS *, int, char **);
  ~FixObmdMerged();

  int setmask();
  void init();
  void pre_exchange();
  void post_force(int);
  void setup(int);
  void *extract(const char *, int &);

```

Several variables, arrays, and parameters are declared as `private` members of the derived class `FixObmdMerged`. Additionally, the following functions are implemented to perform the insertion and deletion of particles, as well as to apply external forces required for imposing boundary conditions:

- `try_deleting()`
- `try_inserting()`
- `usher()`
- `energy()`
- `energy_atomistic_obmd()`
- `reg_force()`
- `reg_force_perp()`
- `g_par_global_charged()`
- `g_par_local_charged()`

- `g_perp_global_charged()`

Each of the functions is explained in detail in the [IMPLEMENTATION FILE](#) section.

IMPLEMENTATION FILE

The implementation of the `FixObmdMerged` class can be found in the `fix_obmd_merged.cpp`, which also contains copyright and license statement and attribution statement with a description of the code base and a brief description of the modifications and adjustments made. The `#include "fix_obmd_merged.h"` statement for the class header is listed first, followed by other essential include statements that provide access to other LAMMPS variables and functions, along with the `#include "pair_lj_cut_rf.h"`. The latter is needed to compute the potential energy of the charged particles to be inserted.

```
#include "fix_obmd_merged.h"

#include "atom.h"
#include "atom_vec.h"
#include "comm.h"
#include "compute.h"
#include "domain.h"
#include "error.h"
#include "fix.h"
#include "force.h"
#include "group.h"
#include "input.h"
#include "lattice.h"
#include "math_const.h"
#include "math_extra.h"
#include "memory.h"
#include "modify.h"
#include "molecule.h"
#include "neighbor.h"
#include "pair.h"
#include "pair_lj_cut_rf.h"
#include "random_park.h"
#include "region.h"
#include "update.h"
#include "variable.h"

#include <cmath>
#include <cstring>
#include <iostream>

using namespace LAMMPS_NS;
using namespace FixConst;
using namespace MathConst;

enum { ATOM, MOLECULE };
enum { DIST_UNIFORM, DIST_GAUSSIAN };
enum { NONE, CONSTANT, EQUAL };
enum { EXCHATOM, EXCHMOL };
enum { MOVEATOM, MOVEMOL };

#define EPSILON 1.0e-6
```

Constructor defined the `obmd` style that inherits from the `Fix` class. The arguments `FIX_ID`, `GROUP_ID`, and `FIX_STYLE = obmd` are read by the parent (i.e., `Fix`) class. To store several variables, the allocation code is added to the constructor.

```
FixObmdMerged::FixObmdMerged(LAMMPS *lmp, int nargs, char **arg) :
    Fix(lmp, nargs, arg), idregion(nullptr), idregion2(nullptr), idregion3(nullptr),
    idregion4(nullptr), idregion5(nullptr), idregion6(nullptr), idrigid(nullptr), idshake(nullptr),
    onemols(nullptr), molfrac(nullptr), coords(nullptr), imageflags(nullptr), fixrigid(nullptr),
    fixshake(nullptr), random(nullptr), list(nullptr), mark(nullptr)
```

In total there are **14 mandatory parameters** (including `FIX_ID`, `GROUP_ID`, and `FIX_STYLE = obmd`), which are specified in and read from the input script.

```
if (nargs < 14) error->all(FLERR, "Illegal fix obmd command (check # of arguments)");
```

These parameters include:

- `ntype` (in the above `e`)
- `nfreq`
- `seed`
- `pxx`
- `pxy`
- `pxz`
- `dpxx`
- `freq`
- `alpha`
- `tau`
- `nbuf`

and several of them can be added as variables when preceded using `"v_"`.

```
ntype = utils::inumeric(FLERR, arg[3], false, lmp);
nfreq = utils::inumeric(FLERR, arg[4], false, lmp);
seed = utils::inumeric(FLERR, arg[5], false, lmp);
if (seed <= 0) error->all(FLERR, "Illegal fix obmd command");

// OBMD settings
if (strstr(arg[6], "v_") == arg[6]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[6][2]) + 1;
    pxxstr = new char[n];
    strcpy(xstr, &arg[6][2]);
} else {
    pxx = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[6], false, lmp);
    pxxstyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[7], "v_") == arg[7]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[7][2]) + 1;
    pxyst = new char[n];
    strcpy(ystr, &arg[7][2]);
} else {
    pxy = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[7], false, lmp);
    pxystyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[8], "v_") == arg[8]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[8][2]) + 1;
    pxzstr = new char[n];
    strcpy(zstr, &arg[8][2]);
} else {
    pxz = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[8], false, lmp);
```

```

    pxzstyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[9], "v_") == arg[9]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[9][2]) + 1;
    dpstr = new char[n];
    strcpy(dpstr, &arg[9][2]);
} else {
    dpxx = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[9], false, lmp);
    dpstyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[10], "v_") == arg[10]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[10][2]) + 1;
    freqstr = new char[n];
    strcpy(freqstr, &arg[10][2]);
} else {
    freq = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[10], false, lmp);
    freqstyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[11], "v_") == arg[11]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[11][2]) + 1;
    alphastr = new char[n];
    strcpy(alphastr, &arg[11][2]);
} else {
    alpha = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[11], false, lmp);
    alphastyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[12], "v_") == arg[12]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[12][2]) + 1;
    taustr = new char[n];
    strcpy(taustr, &arg[12][2]);
} else {
    tau = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[12], false, lmp);
    taustyle = CONSTANT;
}

if (strstr(arg[13], "v_") == arg[13]) {
    int n = strlen(&arg[13][2]) + 1;
    nbufstr = new char[n];
    strcpy(nbufstr, &arg[13][2]);
} else {
    nbuf = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[13], false, lmp);
    nbufstyle = CONSTANT;
}
}

```

If "v_" is defined, the arguments are read as variables and their variable name is stored using the corresponding str string (i.e., pxxstr, pxystr, pxzstr, dpstr, freqstr, alphastr, taustr, and nbufstr). These are utilized in the init() method. The init() method defines the pxxstyle, pxystyle, pxzstyle, dpstyle, freqstyle, alphastyle, taustyle, and nbufstyle variables.

```

/* ----- */
void FixObmdMerged::init()
{
    if (pxxstr) {
        pxxvar = input->variable->find(pxxstr);
        if (pxxvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable name for fix obmd does not exist");
        if (input->variable->equalstyle(pxxvar))
            pxxstyle = EQUAL;
    }
}

```

```
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(pxxvar))
    pxxstyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable for fix obmd is invalid style");
}

if (pxystr) {
pxyvar = input->variable->find(pxystr);
if (pxyvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable name for fix obmd does not exist");
if (input->variable->equalstyle(pxyvar))
    pxystyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(pxyvar))
    pxystyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable for fix obmd is invalid style");
}

if (pxzstr) {
pxzvar = input->variable->find(pxzstr);
if (pxzvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable name for fix obmd does not exist");
if (input->variable->equalstyle(pxzvar))
    pxzstyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(pxzvar))
    pxzstyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable for fix obmd is invalid style");
}

if (dpstr) {
dpvar = input->variable->find(dpstr);
if (dpvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd does not exist", dpstr);
if (input->variable->equalstyle(dpvar))
    dpstyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(dpvar))
    dpstyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd is invalid", dpstr);
}

if (freqstr) {
freqvar = input->variable->find(freqstr);
if (freqvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd does not exist", freqstr);
if (input->variable->equalstyle(freqvar))
    freqstyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(freqvar))
    freqstyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd is invalid", freqstr);
}

if (alphastr) {
alphavar = input->variable->find(alphastr);
if (alphavar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd does not exist", alphastr);
if (input->variable->equalstyle(alphavar))
    alphastyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(alphavar))
    alphastyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd is invalid", alphastr);
}

if (taustr) {
```

```

tauvar = input->variable->find(taustr);
if (tauvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd does not exist", taustr);
if (input->variable->equalstyle(tauvar))
    taustyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(tauvar))
    taustyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd is invalid", taustr);
}

if (nbufstr) {
nbufvar = input->variable->find(nbufstr);
if (nbufvar < 0) error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd does not exist", nbufstr);
if (input->variable->equalstyle(nbufvar))
    nbufstyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(nbufvar))
    nbufstyle = ATOM;
else
    error->all(FLERR, "Variable {} for fix obmd is invalid", nbufstr);
}

```

They can be set to `EQUAL` or `ATOM`, depending whether the variable is of `equal` or `atom` style, and are used in the `pre_exchange()` method.

```

if (input->variable->equalstyle(pxxvar)) pxxstyle = EQUAL;
else if (input->variable->atomstyle(pxxvar)) pxxstyle = ATOM;

```

If `"v_"` is not given, the arguments are treated as numeric constant values.

```

pxx = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[6], false, lmp);
pxxstyle = CONSTANT;

```

In the `init()` method, checks are performed to ensure that the regions required for conducting OBMD simulations are defined, and error is raised if they are not.

```

// get regions
iregion = domain->get_region_by_id(idregion); // LEFT BUFFER
if (!iregion) error->all(FLERR, "Region ID for fix obmd does not exist");

iregion2 = domain->get_region_by_id(idregion2); // RIGHT BUFFER
if (!iregion2) error->all(FLERR, "Region ID for fix obmd does not exist");

iregion3 = domain->get_region_by_id(idregion3); // SHEAR FLOW LEFT
if (!iregion3) error->all(FLERR, "Region ID for fix obmd does not exist");

iregion4 = domain->get_region_by_id(idregion4); // SHEAR FLOW RIGHT
if (!iregion4) error->all(FLERR, "Region ID for fix obmd does not exist");

iregion5 = domain->get_region_by_id(idregion5); // INSERTION LEFT
if (!iregion5) error->all(FLERR, "Region ID for fix obmd does not exist");

iregion6 = domain->get_region_by_id(idregion6); // INSERTION RIGHT
if (!iregion6) error->all(FLERR, "Region ID for fix obmd does not exist");

```

During the OBMD simulation, particles will be deleted from and inserted into the system. Ensuring that the IDs of particles remain unique, the `maxtag_all` (representing current maximal atom ID) or/and `maxmol_all` (representing current maximal molecule ID), is/are also determined (and distributed across all processes).

```

// find current max atom and molecule IDs if necessary
if (idnext) find_maxid();

/* ----- */
void FixObmdMerged::find_maxid()
{
    tagint *tag = atom->tag;
    tagint *molecule = atom->molecule;
    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;

    tagint max = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) max = MAX(max, tag[i]);
    MPI_Allreduce(&max, &maxtag_all, 1, MPI_LMP_TAGINT, MPI_MAX, world);

    if (mode == MOLECULE && molecule) {
        max = 0;
        for (int i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) max = MAX(max, molecule[i]);
        MPI_Allreduce(&max, &maxmol_all, 1, MPI_LMP_TAGINT, MPI_MAX, world);
    }
}

```

The allocated memory is freed in the destructor that follows the constructor.

```

/* ----- */
FixObmdMerged::~FixObmdMerged()
{
    delete random;
    delete[] molfrac;
    delete[] idrigid;
    delete[] idshake;
    delete[] idregion;
    delete[] idregion2;
    delete[] idregion3;
    delete[] idregion4;
    delete[] idregion5;
    delete[] idregion6;
    memory->destroy(coords);
    memory->destroy(imageflags);
    memory->destroy(list);
    memory->destroy(mark);
}

```

The execution of the `obmd fix` during the timestep is controlled by the `setmask()` method. The latter invokes methods of the `FixObmdMerged` class at the `pre_exchange()` and `post_force()` stages of the timestep.

```

/* ----- */
int FixObmdMerged::setmask()
{
    int mask = 0;
    mask |= PRE_EXCHANGE;
    mask |= POST_FORCE;
    return mask;
}

```

The **deletion and insertion of particles should be performed before the neighbor list is rebuilt**, therefore, these routines are implemented in the `pre_exchange()` method. On the other hand, **external forces, which impose the external boundary conditions, should be applied after evaluating the bonded and non-bonded forces**.

Therefore, these forces are applied to the particles in the buffers in the `post_force()` method.

Invoking the `pre_exchange()` method, call to the `try_deleting()` member function is made first. This function takes `Region_id`, `vnewl`, and `vnewr` as arguments. Here, `Region-ID` is set to `iregion` when considering the left buffer, and to `iregion2` when considering the right buffer.

```
/* -----
   perform particle/molecule insertions/deletions
   ----- */
void FixObmdMerged::pre_exchange()
{
    // delete particles that cross the open boundaries after first half of velocity-Verlet
    algorithm
    try_deleting(iregion, vnewl, vnewr);
    try_deleting(iregion2, vnewl, vnewr);
}
```

In the `try_deleting()` member function, a loop over all `nlocal` particles is made. If the particle's position in the open direction (i.e., `x[][0]`, corresponding to the position in the x -direction) is less than the lower limit (`boxl`) or greater than the upper limit (`boxh`) of the simulation box in the x -direction, the particle's local index (`i`) is added to the list of particles that need to be deleted (`list[ncount++] = i`). Each process stores the number of particles to be deleted in variable `ncount`. The total number of particles to be deleted is stored in value `nall`, representing the summed value of `ncount` from all processes. The sum of `ncount` from all processes with lower rank (i.e., the processes before the current one) is stored in `nbefore`.

```
int ncount = 0;
for (i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) {
    if (x[i][0] < boxl || x[i][0] > boxh) {
        std::cout << "Deleting x[i][0] = " << x[i][0] << " i = " << i << " type[i] = " << type[i]
            << " global id = " << atom->tag[i] << std::endl;
        list[ncount++] = i;
    }
}

int nall, nbefore;
MPI_Allreduce(&ncount, &nall, 1, MPI_INT, MPI_SUM, world);
MPI_Scan(&ncount, &nbefore, 1, MPI_INT, MPI_SUM, world);
nbefore -= ncount;
```

After, the deletion is performed. If `mode == ATOM`, the index of a particle to be deleted is randomly chosen across processors and marked for deletion (`mark[] = 1`). Variables `ncount`, `ndel`, and `nall` are updated accordingly. Using the post-decrement operator, the values of `ncount` and `nall` are decreased by 1, while using post-increment operator, the value of variable `del` is increased by 1. The latter stores the total number of deletions performed.

```
// atomic deletions
// choose atoms randomly across all procs and mark them for deletion
// shrink eligible list as my atoms get marked
// keep ndel, ncount, nall, nbefore current after each atom deletion

if (mode == ATOM) {
    while (nall) {
        iwhichglobal = static_cast<int>(nall * random->uniform());
        if (iwhichglobal < nbefore) nbefore--;
        else if (iwhichglobal < nbefore + ncount) {
            iwhichlocal = iwhichglobal - nbefore;
            mark[list[iwhichlocal]] = 1;
            list[iwhichlocal] = list[ncount - 1];
            ncount--;
        }
        ndel++;
        nall--;
    }
}
```

```

    }
}

```

If a molecule is to be deleted, a similar routine is executed, followed by the deletion of bonds, angles, proper dihedral angles, and improper dihedral angles (if any).

The vital part of the implemented OBMD method is monitoring the outgoing linear momentum. The positions (`x[i][0]`) of all `nlocal` particles marked for deletion are extracted and checked to determine if they correspond to the crossing of the outer boundary of the left or right buffer region. If the particle has exited the left buffer, the variable `vnewl` is incremented by its linear momentum, while `vnewr` is incremented if the particle has exited the right buffer.

```

for (i = nlocal - 1; i >= 0; i--) {
  if (mark[i]) {
    if (x[i][0] < 0.5 * (boxh + boxl)) {
      vnewl[0] += mass[type[i]] * vel[i][0];
      vnewl[1] += mass[type[i]] * vel[i][1];
      vnewl[2] += mass[type[i]] * vel[i][2];
    } else {
      vnewr[0] += mass[type[i]] * vel[i][0];
      vnewr[1] += mass[type[i]] * vel[i][1];
      vnewr[2] += mass[type[i]] * vel[i][2];
    }
    avec->copy(atom->nlocal - 1, i, 1);
    atom->nlocal--;
  }
}
}

```

The deletion of particles in the `pre_exchange()` method is followed by the computation of the number of particles to be inserted. The number of particles in the left and right buffer is stored in variables `cnt_left` and `cnt_right`, respectively, which are computed utilizing the `group->count(GROUP_ID, Region-ID)` implemented in the LAMMPS code. Equation

$$\Delta N_b = \frac{\delta t}{\tau_b} (\langle \alpha N_b \rangle - N_b)$$

gives the number of particles to be inserted into the left and right buffer, which are stored in variables `ninsert_left` and `ninsert_right`, respectively.

```

// count number of particles in left/right buffer
cnt_left = group->count(igroup, iregion);
cnt_right = group->count(igroup, iregion2);

// calculate number of particles needed for insertion
ninsert_left = -static_cast<int>((static_cast<double>(cnt_left) / mol_len - alpha * nbuf) *
update->dt / tau);
ninsert_right = -static_cast<int>((static_cast<double>(cnt_right) / mol_len - alpha * nbuf) *
update->dt / tau);

```

By calling `try_inserting()` member function (for each buffer region separately), the insertion procedure starts. The `try_inserting()` method takes `Region-ID`, `ninsert_left/right`, `vnewl`, and `vnewr` as arguments.

```

// tries inserting ninsert_left/right particles into left/right buffer
try_inserting(iregion5, ninsert_left, vnewl, vnewr);
try_inserting(iregion6, ninsert_right, vnewl, vnewr);

```

The `try_inserting()` member function supports both `near` and `usher` insertion algorithms, however, here we focus on the latter. Readers interested in the former are referred to the [LAMMPS documentation](#).

After selecting a random position within the buffer region for the particle to be inserted, its (potential) energy is computed by calling the `usher()` member function and stored in the variable `entmp`.

```

else if (usherflag) {
    me = -1;
    entmp = usher(iregion_var, coords, etarget, natom, imol, iter);
    if (entmp < etarget + EPSILON) {
        if (comm->me == 0)
            std::cout << "USHER accepts at E = " << entmp << " in attempt No. " << attempt << "
with " << iter << " iterations" << std::endl;
    } else {
        if (comm->me == 0)
            std::cout << "USHER denies at E = " << entmp << " at attempt No. " << attempt <<
std::endl;
        flag = 1;
    }
}
}

```

In the `usher()` method, call to `energy_atomistic_obmd()` or `energy()` member function is made. The former is used when simulating **charged particles** and takes the following parameters:

- `iregion_var`
Region ID where particle to be inserted is located.
- `onemols[]->q[]`
Charge of the particle to be inserted.
- `type_temp`
Type of the particle to be inserted.
- `coords[]`
Randomly selected position of the particle to be inserted (vector of length three).
- `fusher`
Force acting on the particle to be inserted.

When simulating **non-charged particles**, the `energy()` member function is called and it takes

- `index`
(Not relevant when simulating DPD particles.)
- `type_temp`
- `coords[]`
- `fusher`

as arguments.

```

if (chargeflag) {
    entmp +=
    energy_atomistic_obmd(iregion_var, onemols[imol]->q[m], type_temp, coords[m], fusher);
} else {
    entmp += energy(1, type_temp, coords[m], fusher); // i - does not matter, itype inserted,
coords[m], fusher
}

```

In the `energy_atomistic_obmd()` member function, the downcast conversion of the pointer to the pair potential class `PairLJCutRF` is made, so that newly added `single_atomistic_obmd()` method implemented in the `PairLJCutRF` class can be accessed.

```

// potential acting between atomistic particles
auto pair = dynamic_cast<PairLJCutRF *>(force->pair_match("lj/cut/rf", 1));

```

Looping over all `nlocal` particles, the distance between the particle to be inserted and the j -th particle of `nlocal` particles is calculated. If the distance (`rsq`) is less than a cutoff (`cutsq`), the energy and the force acting on the particle to be inserted are computed.

```
for (int j = 0; j < nlocal; j++) {
    delx = coord[0] - x[j][0];
    dely = coord[1] - x[j][1];
    delz = coord[2] - x[j][2];

    domain->minimum_image(delx, dely, delz);
    rsq = delx * delx + dely * dely + delz * delz;

    jtype = type[j];

    if (rsq < cutsq[itype][jtype]) {
        total_energy += pair->single_atomistic_obmd(qi, j, itype, jtype, rsq, factor_coul,
        factor_lj, fpair);

        fusher[0] += fpair * delx;
        fusher[1] += fpair * dely;
        fusher[2] += fpair * delz;
    }
}
```

The `energy_atomistic_obmd()` member function returns the total energy of the particle to be inserted, which is stored in variable `total_energy`. Similar is performed when a call to the `energy()` function is made. The computed values of the total energy and force for each process are stored in variables `entmp` and `fusher`, respectively. The summed values of energy and force over all processes are stored in variables `entmp_all` and `fusher_all`, respectively.

```
MPI_Allreduce(fusher, fusher_all, 3, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);
MPI_Allreduce(&entmp, &entmp_all, 1, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);
```

The computed total energy (`entmp_all`) is first compared to the predefined threshold, and if it is lower, the position is accepted and the `usher()` member function is exited.

```
if (entmp_all < etarget + EPSILON) break;
```

Otherwise, the position is iteratively corrected according to the following update rule:

$$\mathbf{r}^{n+1} = \mathbf{r}^n + \frac{\mathbf{f}^n}{|\mathbf{f}^n|} \delta s^n,$$

where displacement δs^n depends on the local potential energy (stored in variable `entmp_all`) and force magnitude (stored in variable `fabs`). If the computed energy is larger than `uovlp`, which is chosen to be a very large energy representing the overlap position, δs^n is computed using

$$\delta s^n = \Delta s_{ovlp} = r_\sigma - \left(\frac{4\varepsilon}{U^n} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

where particle position will be translated for a distance r_σ away from the center of the overlapped particle.

```
else if (entmp_all > uovlp) {
    fabs = sqrt(fusher_all[0] * fusher_all[0] + fusher_all[1] * fusher_all[1] +
    fusher_all[2] * fusher_all[2]);
    if (fabs < EPSILON) continue;
    ds = dsolv - pow(4 * eps / entmp_all, 1.0 / 12.0);

    // loop over atoms of molecule
```

```

for (m = 0; m < natom; m++) {
    coords[m][0] += fusher_all[0] / fabs * ds;
    coords[m][1] += fusher_all[1] / fabs * ds;
    coords[m][2] += fusher_all[2] / fabs * ds;
}
int check = check_mol_region(iregion_var, coords, natom);
if (check == 1) break;    // exit - particle is now within the buffer region
}

```

When the computed energy is lower than u_{ovlp} , δs^n is determined using

$$\delta s^n = \min\left(\Delta s, \frac{U^n - U^0}{|\mathbf{f}^n|}\right).$$

Here, U^0 represents the target energy, which is stored in variable `etarget`, while Δs stands for the displacement step, which is stored in variable `ds0`.

```

else {
    fabs = sqrt(fusher_all[0] * fusher_all[0] + fusher_all[1] * fusher_all[1] + fusher_all[2] *
fusher_all[2]);
    if (fabs < EPSILON) continue;
    ds = std::min((entmp_all - etarget) / fabs, ds0);

    if (mode == MOLECULE) {
        torqabs = sqrt(torq_all[0] * torq_all[0] + torq_all[1] * torq_all[1] + torq_all[2] *
torq_all[2]);
        dtheta = std::min((entmp_all - etarget) / torqabs, dtheta0);
        MathExtra::norm3(torq_all);
        MathExtra::axisangle_to_quat(torq_all, dtheta, quat);
        MathExtra::quat_to_mat(quat, rotmat);
    }

    for (m = 0; m < natom; m++) {
        coords[m][0] += fusher_all[0] / fabs * ds;
        coords[m][1] += fusher_all[1] / fabs * ds;
        coords[m][2] += fusher_all[2] / fabs * ds;

        if (mode == MOLECULE) {
            MathExtra::matvec(rotmat, coords[m], coords_tmp);
            MathExtra::copy3(coords_tmp, coords[m]);
        }
    }
    int check = check_mol_region(iregion_var, coords, natom);
    if (check == 1) break;    // exit
}

```

In case of molecule insertion, rotation of the molecule about its center of mass is also performed. The position obtained by the iterative procedure is verified to remain within the buffer region by calling the `check_mol_region()` member function. If the iterative correction of the position leads to particle leaving the buffer region, the `usher()` method is exited, and the insertion procedure is terminated. On the other hand, if the iterative procedure is successful, a new particle/molecule is inserted. In case of molecule insertion, bonds, angles, proper dihedrals, and improper dihedrals (if any) are also created. As the newly created particles are inserted with zero velocity, the incoming linear momentum is also zero. Therefore, the computed change in the linear momentum comes only from the particles that have exited the outer boundary of the left and right buffer region. Values for the left and right buffer are for each process stored in variables `vnewl` and `vnewr`, respectively, while the corresponding summed values from all processes are stored in variables `vnewl_all` and `vnewr_all`, respectively.

```

MPI_Allreduce(vnewl, vnewl_all, 3, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);
MPI_Allreduce(vnewr, vnewr_all, 3, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);

```

The insertion procedure is followed by the computation of the external forces:

$$\mathbf{F}^{ext} = \sum_{i \in B} \mathbf{f}_i^{ext} = AJ^P \cdot \mathbf{n} - \frac{\sum_{i \in B} \Delta(m_i \mathbf{v}_i)}{\delta t},$$

which are utilized in the `post_force()` method. The first term on the right-hand side of the above equation reads as:

$$AJ^P \cdot \mathbf{n} = p_{xx} A \mathbf{n}.$$

when a system under a constant normal load applied from both sides of the simulation domain is simulated. To introduce a sinusoidal disturbance, it should be rewritten into

$$AJ^P \cdot \mathbf{n} = p_{xx} A \mathbf{n} + \Delta p \sin(2\pi \nu t) A \mathbf{n}$$

while it is expressed as:

$$AJ^P \cdot \mathbf{n} = p_{xx} A \mathbf{n} + p_{xy} A \mathbf{t}$$

when a shear flow is introduced.

```
// area of the buffer - ROI interface
double area = ly * lz;

simulation_time += update->dt;
double factor = pxx + dpxx * sin(2.0 * MY_PI * freq * simulation_time);

// calculates momentum forces on the left buffer
MathExtra::zero3(momentumForce_left);
momentumForce_left[0] = vnewl_all[0] / (update->dt) + factor * area;
momentumForce_left[1] = vnewl_all[1] / (update->dt);
momentumForce_left[2] = vnewl_all[2] / (update->dt);
shearForce_left[0] = 0.0;
shearForce_left[1] = pxy * area;
shearForce_left[2] = pxz * area;

// calculates momentum forces on the right buffer
MathExtra::zero3(momentumForce_right);
momentumForce_right[0] = vnewr_all[0] / (update->dt) - pxx * area; // constant normal load
momentumForce_right[1] = vnewr_all[1] / (update->dt);
momentumForce_right[2] = vnewr_all[2] / (update->dt);
shearForce_right[0] = 0.0;
shearForce_right[1] = -pxy * area;
shearForce_right[2] = -pxz * area;
```

Variables `momentumForce[]_left/right` and `shearForce_left/right[]` represent the array of length three and carry information about the external boundary condition of the constant normal load (or mechanical pressure wave) and shear stress to be applied in the x -, y -, and z -directions, respectively.

The `obmd fix` is also executed at the `post_force()` stage of the timestep, as defined in the `setmask()` method. At this stage, external forces computed in the `pre_exchange()` method are applied to the particles in the buffers. Forces acting in normal direction are distributed first by calling the `reg_force()` member function, which takes `Region-ID`, `momentumForce_left/right`, and `step_parallel` as arguments. Here, `Region-ID` denotes `iregion` corresponding to the left buffer region, where the total external force stored in variable `momentumForce_left` will be applied. The same applies to the imposition of the total external force (`momentumForce_right`) to the right buffer. The `step_parallel` parameter defines the weighting function used to distribute the total external force among particles within the buffers.

```
/* ----- */
void FixObmdMerged::post_force(int vflag)
{
    if (update->timestep % nevery) { return; }
}
```

```
// parallel forces
reg_force(vflag, iregion, momentumForce_left, step_parallel);
reg_force(vflag, iregion2, momentumForce_right, step_parallel);
```

In the `reg_force()` method the total mass of particles in the corresponding buffer is computed by calling the `g_par_global_charged()` member function. The computed value is stored in variable `gtmp`.

```
/* ----- */
void FixObmdMerged::reg_force(int vflag, Region *region, double *momentumForce, int step)
{
    if (region) region->prematch();
    v_init(vflag);

    double **x = atom->x;
    double **f = atom->f;
    double *mass = atom->mass;
    int *mask = atom->mask;
    imageint *image = atom->image;
    double v[6];
    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;
    double mass_tmp;
    int *type = atom->type;
    double gtmp = g_par_global_charged(region, step);
    double gloctmp;
    double unwrap[3];
    double xval, yval, zval;
```

For now, only **smooth weighting function** is enabled (i.e., `step_parallel == 0`), where parameter `gfac` is used to define the region in which the position dependent sigmoidal function is multiplied with the mass of a particle.

```
/* ----- */
double FixObmdMerged::g_par_global_charged(Region *region, int step)
{
    if (region) region->prematch();

    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;
    tagint *molecule = atom->molecule;
    int *rep_atom = atom->rep_atom;
    double **cms = atom->cms_mol;
    double *mass = atom->mass;
    int *type = atom->type;
    double **x = atom->x;
    int imol;
    int *tag = atom->tag;
    double **f = atom->f;

    double upper_x = domain->boxhi[0]; // upper
    double lower_x = domain->boxlo[0]; // lower

    // init for distribution function
    double g_par_all = 0.0;
    double g_par_all_tmp = 0.0;

    // for now only smooth transition -> ADD for step = 1
    double carg;
    if (!step) {
        for (int i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) {
            // mass of a particle
```

```

double mass_temp = mass[type[i]];

// (looping over nlocals) check if in prescribed region, continue if not
if (region && !region->match(x[i][0], x[i][1], x[i][2])) continue;

// if here ... molecule in buffer
if (x[i][0] < lower_x + buffer_size) { // LEFT BUFFER
    if (x[i][0] < (lower_x + (1.0 - g_fac) * buffer_size)) { // only mass
        g_par_all += mass_temp;
    } else { // sigmoidal mass
        carg = 1.0 / g_fac * MY_PI * (x[i][0] - buffer_size - lower_x) / (-buffer_size) -
MY_PI;

        g_par_all += 0.5 * (1.0 + cos(carg)) * mass_temp;
    }
}
if (x[i][0] > upper_x - buffer_size) { // RIGHT BUFFER
    if (x[i][0] > (upper_x - (1.0 - g_fac) * buffer_size)) {
        g_par_all += mass_temp;
    } else {
        carg = 1.0 / g_fac * MY_PI * (x[i][0] - upper_x + buffer_size) / (buffer_size)
-MY_PI;

        g_par_all += 0.5 * (1.0 + cos(carg)) * mass_temp;
    }
}
}
// OTHER IS NOT OF MY INTEREST ... ROI
}
} else {
    error->all(FLERR, "For now implemented only for !step");
}
// sum and distribute
MPI_Allreduce(&g_par_all, &g_par_all_tmp, 1, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);

return g_par_all_tmp;
}

```

The total mass computed by each process is stored in variable `g_par_all`, while the value returned by the `g_par_global_charged()` method is stored in variable `g_par_all_tmp`, which represents the summed value of `g_par_all` from all processes.

In the `reg_force()` member function, the mass (or weighted mass) of a particle in the buffer region (stored in variable `gloctmp`) is divided by the total mass of the buffer region (`gtmp`), which is computed by calling the `g_par_global_charged()` method. Multiplying this ratio by the `momentumForce_left/right` yields the force acting on the particle within the corresponding buffer region.

```

for (int i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) {
    if (region && !region->match(x[i][0], x[i][1], x[i][2])) continue;
    domain->unmap(x[i], image[i], unwrap);
    mass_temp = mass[type[i]];
    if (mode == MOLECULE) mass_temp = mtot;

    gloctmp = g_par_local_charged(mass[type[i]], region, x[i][0], step);

    xval = momentumForce[0] * gloctmp / gtmp;
    yval = momentumForce[1] * gloctmp / gtmp;
    zval = momentumForce[2] * gloctmp / gtmp;
}

```

The latter is applied to each particle within the buffer region.

```

f[i][0] += xval;
f[i][1] += yval;

```

```
f[i][2] += zval;
```

To impose shear stress, the `reg_force_perp()` member function is called separately for each buffer region in the `post_force()` method. It takes `vflag`, `Region-ID`, `shearForce_left/right`, and `step_perp` as arguments. Here, the `step_perp` parameter defines the weighting function that is used to distribute shear forces (stored in `shearForce_left/right` representing the array of length three) among particles in the buffer regions.

```
// tangential forces
reg_force_perp(vflag, iregion3, shearForce_left, step_perp);
reg_force_perp(vflag, iregion4, shearForce_right, step_perp);
```

In the `reg_force_perp()` member function the total mass of particles in the corresponding buffer is computed by summing their masses by calling the `g_perp_global_charged()` member function. The computed value is stored in variable `gtmp`.

```
/* ----- */
void FixObmdMerged::reg_force_perp(int vflag, Region *region, double *shearForce, int step)
{
    if (region) region->prematch();
    v_init(vflag);

    double **x = atom->x;
    double **f = atom->f;
    double *mass = atom->mass;
    int *mask = atom->mask;
    imageint *image = atom->image;
    double v[6];
    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;
    int *type = atom->type;
    double gtmp = g_perp_global_charged(region, step);
    double mass_tmp, gloctmp;
    double unwrap[3];
    double xval, yval, zval;
```

For now, only **Heaviside step function** is enabled (i.e., `step_perp == 1`).

```
/* ----- */
double FixObmdMerged::g_perp_global_charged(Region *iregion_var, int step)
{
    if (iregion_var) iregion_var->prematch();

    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;
    tagint *molecule = atom->molecule;
    double *mass = atom->mass;
    int *type = atom->type;
    double **x = atom->x;
    int imol;
    int *tag = atom->tag;
    double **f = atom->f;

    double upper_x = domain->boxhi[0];
    double lower_x = domain->boxlo[0];

    double g_perp_all = 0.0;
    double g_perp_all_tmp = 0.0;

    if (step) {
```

```

    for (int i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) {

        // mass of a particle
        double mass_tmp = mass[type[i]];

        if (iregion_var && !iregion_var->match(x[i][0], x[i][1], x[i][2])) continue;
        g_perp_all += mass_tmp;
    }
} else {
    error->all(FLERR, "For now implemented only for step");
}

// sum and distribute
MPI_Allreduce(&g_perp_all, &g_perp_all_tmp, 1, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);
return g_perp_all_tmp;
}

```

In the same manner as before, the total mass computed by each process is stored in variable `g_perp_all`, while the value returned by the `g_perp_global_charged()` method is stored in the variable `g_perp_all_tmp`, representing the summed value of `g_perp_all` from all processes. Shear forces are distributed by calling the `reg_force_perp()` member function. This routine follows the same approach as the one presented above for calling `reg_force()`, except this time, `shearForce_left/right` are utilized.

```

/* ----- */
void FixObndMerged::reg_force_perp(int vflag, Region *region, double *shearForce, int step)
{
    if (region) region->prematch();
    v_init(vflag);

    double **x = atom->x;
    double **f = atom->f;
    double *mass = atom->mass;
    int *mask = atom->mask;
    imageint *image = atom->image;
    double v[6];
    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;
    int *type = atom->type;
    double gtmp = g_perp_global_charged(region, step);
    double mass_tmp, gloctmp;
    double unwrap[3];
    double xval, yval, zval;

    for (int i = 0; i < nlocal; i++) {
        if (region && !region->match(x[i][0], x[i][1], x[i][2])) continue;
        domain->unmap(x[i], image[i], unwrap);

        gloctmp = mass[type[i]];

        xval = shearForce[0] * gloctmp / gtmp;
        yval = shearForce[1] * gloctmp / gtmp;
        zval = shearForce[2] * gloctmp / gtmp;

        f[i][0] += xval;
        f[i][1] += yval;
        f[i][2] += zval;

        if (evflag) {
            v[0] = xval * unwrap[0];
            v[1] = yval * unwrap[1];
            v[2] = zval * unwrap[2];
            v[3] = xval * unwrap[1];

```

```

        v[4] = xval * unwrap[2];
        v[5] = yval * unwrap[2];
        v_tally(i, v);
    }
}
}

```

If you are using `fix obmd`, please **cite the following articles**:

- R. Delgado-Buscalioni, J. Sablić, and M. Praprotnik, *Eur. Phys. J. Special Topics* **224**, 2331-2349 (2015).
- R. Delgado-Buscalioni, K. Kremer, and M. Praprotnik, *J. Chem. Phys.* **128**, 114110 (2008).
- J. Sablić, M. Praprotnik, and R. Delgado-Buscalioni, *Soft Matter* **12**, 2416-2439 (2016).
- L. Delle Site and M. Praprotnik, *Phys. Rep.* **693**, 1-56 (2017).
- P. Papež and M. Praprotnik, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **18**, 1227-1240 (2022).
- R. Delgado-Buscalioni and P. V. Coveney, *J. Chem. Phys.* **119**, 978-987 (2003).

PAIR STYLE `lj/cut/rf`

Because in the open-boundary molecular dynamics (OBMD), electrostatic interactions are treated using reaction field (rf) method, the latter was implemented as a `lj/cut/rf` pair style and added to the `src`.

Pair style `lj/cut/rf` is derived from the `Pair` class, and it is **used to compute the Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential and treat electrostatic interactions using the rf method**.

$$U_{rf}(r_{i\alpha j\beta}) = \frac{q_{i\alpha}q_{j\beta}}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_{i\alpha j\beta}} \left[1 + \frac{\epsilon_{rf} - 1}{2\epsilon_{rf} + 1} \left(\frac{r_{i\alpha j\beta}}{r_c} \right)^3 \right] - \frac{q_{i\alpha}q_{j\beta}}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_c} \frac{3\epsilon_{rf}}{2\epsilon_{rf} + 1}$$

Here, q , ϵ_0 , and ϵ_{rf} stand for the electric charge, vacuum permittivity, and dielectric constant, respectively.

The input script syntax reads as

```

pair_style lj/cut/rf rc_lj rc_rf
pair_coeff TYPE1 TYPE2 epsilon sigma rc_lj rc_rf epsilon_rf

```

The newly implemented pair style takes the following arguments:

- `rc_lj`
Cutoff of the LJ interaction.
- `rc_rf`
Cutoff of the electrostatic interaction.

For each pair of atom types (defined by `TYPE1` and `TYPE2`), the following coefficients must be determined:

- `epsilon`
(Energy units.)
- `sigma`
(Distance units.)
- `rc_lj`
(Distance units and optional parameter.)
- `rc_rf`
(Distance units and optional parameter.)
- `epsilon_rf`
Dielectric permittivity.

The class name of the `lj/cut/rf` pair style is `PairLJCutRF` and source files are `pair_lj_cut_rf.cpp` and `pair_lj_cut_rf.h`.

HEADER FILE

The first segment of the header file contains the copyright, license statement and attribution.

```

/* -*- c++ -*- -----
LAMMPS - Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator
https://www.lammps.org/, Sandia National Laboratories
LAMMPS development team: developers@lammps.org

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Attribution:
- Original code by Sandia Corporation.
- lj/cut/rf uses portions of code derived from lj/cut/coul/cut pair style:
https://docs.lammps.org/pair_lj_cut_coul.html

See the README file in the top-level LAMMPS directory.
----- */

```

Inclusion of the following lines in the second part of the header file registers pair style `lj/cut/rf` with LAMMPS. This block is included by the `Force` class in `force.cpp` that creates an instance of the `PairLJCutRF` class and returns a pointer to it, and connects the name of the `lj/cut/rf` pair style to the `PairLJCutRF` class.

```

#ifdef PAIR_CLASS
// clang-format off
PairStyle(lj/cut/rf,PairLJCutRF);
// clang-format on
#else

// Content

#endif

```

The `// Content` part of the header file represents an actual definition of the `PairLJCutRF` class. The `PairLJCutRF` class includes required (i.e., `compute`, `settings`, and `coeff`) and some additional (i.e., `init_one`, `single`, `single_atomistic_obmd`, and `extract`) member functions. Several variables, arrays, and interaction parameters are declared as protected members of the derived `PairLJCutRF` class.

```

#ifndef LMP_PAIR_LJ_CUT_RF_H
#define LMP_PAIR_LJ_CUT_RF_H

#include "pair.h"

namespace LAMMPS_NS {

class PairLJCutRF : public Pair {
public:
    PairLJCutRF(class LAMMPS *);
    ~PairLJCutRF() override;
    void compute(int, int) override;
    void settings(int, char **) override;
    void coeff(int, char **) override;
    void init_style() override;
    double init_one(int, int) override;

```

```

void write_restart(FILE *) override;
void read_restart(FILE *) override;
void write_restart_settings(FILE *) override;
void read_restart_settings(FILE *) override;
void write_data(FILE *) override;
void write_data_all(FILE *) override;
double single(int, int, int, int, double, double, double, double &) override;
double single_atomistic_obmd(double, int, int, int, double, double, double, double &); //
PP
void born_matrix(int, int, int, int, double, double, double, double &, double &) override;
void *extract(const char *, int &) override;
protected:
double cut_lj_global, cut_coul_global;
double **cut_lj, **cut_ljsq;
double **cut_coul, **cut_coulsq;
double **epsilon, **sigma;
double **lj1, **lj2, **lj3, **lj4, **offset;

// for reaction field
double epsilon_rf_one;
double **epsilon_rf;
virtual void allocate();
};

} // namespace LAMMPS_NS

#endif
#endif

```

IMPLEMENTATION FILE

In the `pair_lj_cut_rf.cpp`, the implementation of the `PairLJCutRF` class can be found. The `pair_lj_cut_rf.cpp` file also contains copyright, license statement, and attribution with several include statements, where `#include "pair_lj_cut_rf.h"` for the class header is listed first.

```

#include "pair_lj_cut_rf.h"

#include "atom.h"
#include "comm.h"
#include "error.h"
#include "force.h"
#include "math_const.h"
#include "memory.h"
#include "neigh_list.h"
#include "neighbor.h"
#include <cmath>
#include <cstring>

#include <iostream>

using namespace LAMMPS_NS;
using namespace MathConst;

```

The first section of the implementation file is followed by constructor of the `PairLJCutRF` class, which takes the LAMMPS class instance pointer `*lmp` as an argument.

```

/* ----- */
PairLJCutRF::PairLJCutRF(LAMMPS *lmp) : Pair(lmp)
{
    born_matrix_enable = 1;

```

```
writedata = 1;
}
```

In destructor the memory allocated to the objects of `lj/cut/rf` pair style is freed.

```
/* ----- */
PairLJCutRF::~PairLJCutRF()
{
    if (copymode) return;

    if (allocated) {
        memory->destroy(setflag);
        memory->destroy(cutsq);

        memory->destroy(cut_lj);
        memory->destroy(cut_ljsq);
        memory->destroy(cut_coul);
        memory->destroy(cut_coulsq);
        memory->destroy(epsilon);
        memory->destroy(sigma);
        memory->destroy(lj1);
        memory->destroy(lj2);
        memory->destroy(lj3);
        memory->destroy(lj4);
        memory->destroy(offset);

        memory->destroy(epsilon_rf);
    }
}
```

The arguments of the `pair_style lj/cut/rf` command are processed in the `settings()` member function. Here, global parameters (to define cutoffs) are set.

```
/* -----
   global settings
   ----- */
void PairLJCutRF::settings(int narg, char **arg)
{
    if (narg < 1 || narg > 2) error->all(FLERR, "Illegal pair_style command");

    cut_lj_global = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[0], false, lmp);
    if (narg == 1)
        cut_coul_global = cut_lj_global;
    else
        cut_coul_global = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[1], false, lmp);

    // reset cutoffs that have been explicitly set

    if (allocated) {
        int i, j;
        for (i = 1; i <= atom->ntypes; i++)
            for (j = i; j <= atom->ntypes; j++)
                if (setflag[i][j]) {
                    cut_lj[i][j] = cut_lj_global;
                    cut_coul[i][j] = cut_coul_global;
                }
    }
}
```

The `allocate()` member function handles memory allocation.

```

/* -----
   allocate all arrays
   ----- */

void PairLJCutRF::allocate()
{
    allocated = 1;
    int np1 = atom->ntypes + 1;

    memory->create(setflag, np1, np1, "pair:setflag");
    for (int i = 1; i < np1; i++)
        for (int j = i; j < np1; j++) setflag[i][j] = 0;

    memory->create(cutsq, np1, np1, "pair:cutsq");
    memory->create(cut_lj, np1, np1, "pair:cut_lj");
    memory->create(cut_ljsq, np1, np1, "pair:cut_ljsq");
    memory->create(cut_coul, np1, np1, "pair:cut_coul");
    memory->create(cut_coulsq, np1, np1, "pair:cut_coulsq");
    memory->create(epsilon, np1, np1, "pair:epsilon");
    memory->create(sigma, np1, np1, "pair:sigma");
    memory->create(lj1, np1, np1, "pair:lj1");
    memory->create(lj2, np1, np1, "pair:lj2");
    memory->create(lj3, np1, np1, "pair:lj3");
    memory->create(lj4, np1, np1, "pair:lj4");
    memory->create(offset, np1, np1, "pair:offset");
    memory->create(epsilon_rf, np1, np1, "pair:epsilon_rf");
}

```

While the arguments of the `pair_style lj/cut/rf` command are processed in the `settings()` method, the arguments provided to the `pair_coeff` command are handled in the `coeff()` member function. A total of **5 or 7 arguments** should be provided to the `pair_coeff` command, where global cutoffs are set as default, i.e., `cut_lj_one = cut_lj_global` and `cut_coul_one = cut_coul_global`, unless the sixth and seventh parameter are specified. Therefore, if the `rc_lj` and `rc_rf` arguments are not provided, the global LJ and rf cutoffs specified in the `pair_style` command are utilized. If only one cutoff is given, it is applied for both interactions. If both cutoffs are provided, they are used as the LJ and rf cutoffs for this type pair. Ultimately, the 2D arrays, namely `epsilon`, `sigma`, `cut_lj`, `cut_coul`, and `epsilon_rf`, are created for each atom pair.

```

/* -----
   set coeffs for one or more type pairs
   ----- */

void PairLJCutRF::coeff(int narg, char **arg)
{
    if (narg < 5 || narg > 7) error->all(FLERR, "Incorrect args for pair coefficients");
    if (!allocated) allocate();

    int ilo, ihi, jlo, jhi;
    utils::bounds(FLERR, arg[0], 1, atom->ntypes, ilo, ihi, error);
    utils::bounds(FLERR, arg[1], 1, atom->ntypes, jlo, jhi, error);

    double epsilon_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[2], false, lmp);
    double sigma_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[3], false, lmp);

    double cut_lj_one = cut_lj_global;
    double cut_coul_one = cut_coul_global;
    epsilon_rf_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[4], false, lmp);

    if (narg >= 6) {
        cut_coul_one = cut_lj_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[4], false, lmp);
    }
}

```

```

    epsilon_rf_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[5], false, lmp);
  }
  if (narg == 7) {
    cut_lj_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[4], false, lmp);
    cut_coul_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[5], false, lmp);
    epsilon_rf_one = utils::numeric(FLERR, arg[6], false, lmp);
  }

  int count = 0;
  for (int i = ilo; i <= ihi; i++) {
    for (int j = MAX(jlo, i); j <= jhi; j++) {
      epsilon[i][j] = epsilon_one;
      sigma[i][j] = sigma_one;
      cut_lj[i][j] = cut_lj_one;
      cut_coul[i][j] = cut_coul_one;

      // reaction field param
      epsilon_rf[i][j] = epsilon_rf_one;

      setflag[i][j] = 1;
      count++;
    }
  }

  if (count == 0) error->all(FLERR, "Incorrect args for pair coefficients");
}

```

The completeness of the potential parameters is verified in the `init_one()` method. This method invokes the `Pair::mix_energy()` and `Pair::mix_distance()` member functions if the `setflag` for particle pairs is 0 or if the command `pair_modify mix {geometric,arithmetic,sixthpower}` is used. Additionally, the quantities `cut_ljsq`, `cut_coulsq`, `lj1`, `lj2`, `lj3`, and `lj4` are defined and stored as 2D arrays. The offset to shift the LJ potential value to zero at the cutoff distance is computed when the `pair_modify shift yes` command is employed. Finally, the potential parameters arrays are symmetrized.

```

/* -----
   init for one type pair i,j and corresponding j,i
   ----- */
double PairLJCutRF::init_one(int i, int j)
{
  if (setflag[i][j] == 0) {
    epsilon[i][j] = mix_energy(epsilon[i][i], epsilon[j][j], sigma[i][i], sigma[j][j]);
    sigma[i][j] = mix_distance(sigma[i][i], sigma[j][j]);
    cut_lj[i][j] = mix_distance(cut_lj[i][i], cut_lj[j][j]);
    cut_coul[i][j] = mix_distance(cut_coul[i][i], cut_coul[j][j]);
  }

  double cut = MAX(cut_lj[i][j], cut_coul[i][j]);
  cut_ljsq[i][j] = cut_lj[i][j] * cut_lj[i][j];
  cut_coulsq[i][j] = cut_coul[i][j] * cut_coul[i][j];

  lj1[i][j] = 48.0 * epsilon[i][j] * pow(sigma[i][j], 12.0);
  lj2[i][j] = 24.0 * epsilon[i][j] * pow(sigma[i][j], 6.0);
  lj3[i][j] = 4.0 * epsilon[i][j] * pow(sigma[i][j], 12.0);
  lj4[i][j] = 4.0 * epsilon[i][j] * pow(sigma[i][j], 6.0);

  if (offset_flag && (cut_lj[i][j] > 0.0)) {
    double ratio = sigma[i][j] / cut_lj[i][j];
    offset[i][j] = 4.0 * epsilon[i][j] * (pow(ratio, 12.0) - pow(ratio, 6.0));
  } else
    offset[i][j] = 0.0;
}

```

```

cut_ljsq[j][i] = cut_ljsq[i][j];
cut_coul[j][i] = cut_coul[i][j];
cut_coulsq[j][i] = cut_coulsq[i][j];
lj1[j][i] = lj1[i][j];
lj2[j][i] = lj2[i][j];
lj3[j][i] = lj3[i][j];
lj4[j][i] = lj4[i][j];

epsilon_rf[j][i] = epsilon_rf[i][j];

offset[j][i] = offset[i][j];

// compute I,J contribution to long-range tail correction
// count total # of atoms of type I and J via Allreduce

if (tail_flag) {
    int *type = atom->type;
    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;

    double count[2], all[2];
    count[0] = count[1] = 0.0;
    for (int k = 0; k < nlocal; k++) {
        if (type[k] == i) count[0] += 1.0;
        if (type[k] == j) count[1] += 1.0;
    }
    MPI_Allreduce(count, all, 2, MPI_DOUBLE, MPI_SUM, world);

    double sig2 = sigma[i][j] * sigma[i][j];
    double sig6 = sig2 * sig2 * sig2;
    double rc3 = cut_lj[i][j] * cut_lj[i][j] * cut_lj[i][j];
    double rc6 = rc3 * rc3;
    double rc9 = rc3 * rc6;
    etail_ij =
    8.0 * MY_PI * all[0] * all[1] * epsilon[i][j] * sig6 * (sig6 - 3.0 * rc6) / (9.0 * rc9);
    ptail_ij = 16.0 * MY_PI * all[0] * all[1] * epsilon[i][j] * sig6 * (2.0 * sig6 - 3.0 *
rc6) /
    (9.0 * rc9);
    }

    return cut;
}

```

The pairwise forces and potential between atoms i and j are computed in the `compute()` method. The charge (q), position vector components (in x -, y -, z -directions, i.e., $x[][0]$, $x[][1]$, $x[][2]$, respectively), and neighbors of the central atom i are extracted by applying a for loop over all central atoms. Applying an additional for loop over neighbors j of atom i , the square of the distance between atoms i and j is computed and stored in variable `rsq`. The computed distance is compared with the cutoff distance, and if it is smaller, force between atoms i and j is evaluated. Focusing only on the computation of the rf contribution, the following variables are defined:

- `rf_fctr_0`

$$rf_fctr_0 = \frac{1}{r_c^3}$$

- `rf_fctr_1`

$$rf_fctr_1 = \epsilon_{rf} - 1$$

- `rf_fctr_2`

$$rf_fctr_2 = 1 + 2\epsilon_{rf}$$

and the `forcecoul` variable is calculated using

$$F_{rf}(r_{i\alpha j\beta}) = \frac{q_{i\alpha}q_{j\beta}}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left[\frac{1}{r_{i\alpha j\beta}^3} - \frac{1}{r_c^3} \frac{2(\epsilon_{rf} - 1)}{2\epsilon_{rf} + 1} \right] \mathbf{r}_{i\alpha j\beta}.$$

The obtained force is scaled by `factor_coul` and added to the `fpairlj`, defining the `fpair` variable. The `fpair` variable is further multiplied with the displacement vector components (`delx`, `dely`, and `delz`), and forces acting in x -, y -, and z -directions are assigned to atom i . If command `newton_pair` on is specified, forces acting in the opposite directions are applied to the atom j . When energy contributions are requested (i.e., when `eflag = 1`), the energy interaction between atoms i and j is also computed.

```

/* ----- */

void PairLJCutRF::compute(int eflag, int vflag)
{
    std::cout<<"compute"<<"\n";
    int i, j, ii, jj, inum, jnum, itype, jtype;
    double qtmp, xtmp, ytmp, ztmp, delx, dely, delz, evdwl, ecoul, fpair;
    double rsq, r2inv, r6inv, forcecoul, forcelj, factor_coul, factor_lj;
    int *ilist, *jlist, *numneigh, **firstneigh;

    double fpairlj, fpaircoul;
    evdwl = ecoul = 0.0;
    ev_init(eflag, vflag);

    double **x = atom->x;
    double **f = atom->f;
    double *q = atom->q;
    int *type = atom->type;
    int nlocal = atom->nlocal;
    double *special_coul = force->special_coul;
    double *special_lj = force->special_lj;
    int newton_pair = force->newton_pair;
    double qprd2e = force->qprd2e;

    inum = list->inum;
    ilist = list->ilist;
    numneigh = list->numneigh;
    firstneigh = list->firstneigh;

    // loop over neighbors of my atoms

    for (ii = 0; ii < inum; ii++) {
        i = ilist[ii];
        qtmp = q[i];
        xtmp = x[i][0];
        ytmp = x[i][1];
        ztmp = x[i][2];
        itype = type[i];
        jlist = firstneigh[i];
        jnum = numneigh[i];

        for (jj = 0; jj < jnum; jj++) {
            j = jlist[jj];
            factor_lj = special_lj[sbmask(j)];
            factor_coul = special_coul[sbmask(j)];
            j &= NEIGHMASK;

            delx = xtmp - x[j][0];

```

```

dely = ytmp - x[j][1];
delz = ztmp - x[j][2];
rsq = delx * delx + dely * dely + delz * delz;
jtype = type[j];

if (rsq < cutsq[itYPE][jtype]) {
    r2inv = 1.0 / rsq;

    // terms for reaction field
    double rf_fctr_0 = 1.0 / pow(sqrt(rsq),3.0);
    double rf_fctr_1 = (epsilon_rf[itYPE][jtype] - 1.0);
    double rf_fctr_2 = 1.0 + 2.0 * epsilon_rf[itYPE][jtype];

    if (rsq < cut_coulsq[itYPE][jtype]) {
        forcecoul = (qqr2e * qtmp * q[j]) * ((r2inv*sqrt(r2inv)) - (1.0 /
pow(cut_coul[itYPE][jtype],3.0) * (2.0 * rf_fctr_1 / rf_fctr_2)));
    }
    else {
        forcecoul = 0.0;
    }

    if (rsq < cut_ljsq[itYPE][jtype]) {
        r6inv = r2inv * r2inv * r2inv;
        forcelj = r6inv * (lj1[itYPE][jtype] * r6inv - lj2[itYPE][jtype]);
    } else
        forcelj = 0.0;

    fpairlj = factor_lj * forcelj * r2inv;
    fpaircoul = factor_coul * forcecoul;
    fpair = fpairlj + fpaircoul;

    f[i][0] += delx * fpair;
    f[i][1] += dely * fpair;
    f[i][2] += delz * fpair;
    if (newton_pair || j < nlocal) {
        f[j][0] -= delx * fpair;
        f[j][1] -= dely * fpair;
        f[j][2] -= delz * fpair;
    }

    if (f[i][0] > 10000 || f[i][1] > 10000 || f[i][2] > 10000) {
        std::cout<<"PairLJCutRF::compute"<<"\n";
        std::cout<<"f[i][0]: "<<f[i][0]<<"\n";
        std::cout<<"f[i][1]: "<<f[i][1]<<"\n";
        std::cout<<"f[i][2]: "<<f[i][2]<<"\n";
    }

    if (eflag) {
        if (rsq < cut_coulsq[itYPE][jtype]) {
            ecoul = (qqr2e * qtmp * q[j]) * sqrt(r2inv) * (1.0 + (rf_fctr_1 / rf_fctr_2)
* (pow(sqrt(rsq)/cut_coul[itYPE][jtype],3.0)))
            - (qqr2e * qtmp * q[j]) * (1.0 / cut_coul[itYPE][jtype]) * (3.0 *
epsilon_rf[itYPE][jtype] / rf_fctr_2);
            ecoul *= factor_coul;
        }
        else {
            ecoul = 0.0;
        }

        if (rsq < cut_ljsq[itYPE][jtype]) {
            evdwl = r6inv * (lj3[itYPE][jtype] * r6inv - lj4[itYPE][jtype]) -
offset[itYPE][jtype];
            evdwl *= factor_lj;
        }
    }
}

```

```

        } else
            evdwl = 0.0;
        }

        if (evflag) ev_tally(i, j, nlocal, newton_pair, evdwl, ecoul, fpair, delx, dely,
delz);
    }
}
}

if (vflag_fdotr) virial_fdotr_compute();
}

```

Other classes can access potential energy by calling `single()` member function. Again, focusing only on the rf method, the energy is computed as

$$U_{rf}(r_{\alpha j \beta}) = \frac{q_{\alpha} q_{j \beta}}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_{\alpha j \beta}} \left[1 + \frac{\epsilon_{rf} - 1}{2\epsilon_{rf} + 1} \left(\frac{r_{\alpha j \beta}}{r_c} \right)^3 \right] - \frac{q_{\alpha} q_{j \beta}}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_c} \frac{3\epsilon_{rf}}{2\epsilon_{rf} + 1}$$

and scaled by factor `factor_coul`. The `single()` method returns the interaction energy stored in variable `eng`, which represents a sum of the LJ and rf energy terms.

```

/* ----- */
double PairLJCutRF::single(int i, int j, int itype, int jtype, double rsq, double factor_coul,
double factor_lj, double &fforce)
{
    double r2inv, r6inv, forcecoul, forcelj, phicoul, philj;
    double rf_fctr_1 = (epsilon_rf[itype][jtype] - 1.0);
    double rf_fctr_2 = 1.0 + 2.0 * epsilon_rf[itype][jtype];
    r2inv = 1.0 / rsq;

    if (rsq < cut_coulsq[itype][jtype]) {
        forcecoul = (force->qrd2e * atom->q[i] * atom->q[j])
            * (r2inv * sqrt(r2inv)
            - (1.0 / pow(cut_coul[itype][jtype], 3.0)) * (2.0 * rf_fctr_1 / rf_fctr_2));
    }
    else {
        forcecoul = 0.0;
    }

    if (rsq < cut_ljsq[itype][jtype]) {
        r6inv = r2inv * r2inv * r2inv;
        forcelj = r6inv * (lj1[itype][jtype] * r6inv - lj2[itype][jtype]);
    } else
        forcelj = 0.0;

    fforce = factor_coul * forcecoul + factor_lj * forcelj * r2inv;

    double eng = 0.0;
    if (rsq < cut_coulsq[itype][jtype]) {
        phicoul = force->qrd2e * atom->q[i] * atom->q[j] * sqrt(r2inv) * (1.0 + (rf_fctr_1 /
rf_fctr_2) * (pow(sqrt(rsq)/cut_coul[itype][jtype], 3.0)))
            - force->qrd2e * atom->q[i] * atom->q[j] * (1.0 / cut_coul[itype][jtype]) * (3.0 *
epsilon_rf[itype][jtype] / rf_fctr_2);
        eng += factor_coul * phicoul;
    }
    if (rsq < cut_ljsq[itype][jtype]) {
        philj = r6inv * (lj3[itype][jtype] * r6inv - lj4[itype][jtype]) - offset[itype][jtype];
        eng += factor_lj * philj;
    }
}

```

```

return eng;
}

```

To compute the energy of a particle to be inserted during OBMD simulations, an additional method called `single_atomistic_obmd()` has been implemented. The key difference between `single_atomistic_obmd()` and the `single()` method lies in the arguments that these member functions accept. While the `single()` member function takes (local) indices of atoms i and j , the `single_atomistic_obmd()` function requires the charge of particle i (q_i) to be inserted instead of index i . It is important to note that in this case, the particle " i " does not yet exist.

```

/* ----- */
double PairLJCutRF::single_atomistic_obmd(double qi, int j, int itype, int jtype, double rsq,
double factor_coul,
double factor_lj, double &fforce)
{
    double r2inv, r6inv, forcecoul, forcelj, phicoul, philj;

    double rf_fctr_1 = (epsilon_rf[itype][jtype] - 1.0);
    double rf_fctr_2 = 1.0 + 2.0 * epsilon_rf[itype][jtype];

    r2inv = 1.0 / rsq;
    if (rsq < cut_coulsq[itype][jtype]) {
        forcecoul = (force->qrd2e * qi * atom->q[j])
* (r2inv*sqrt(r2inv)
- (1.0 / pow(cut_coul[itype][jtype],3.0) * (2.0 * rf_fctr_1 / rf_fctr_2)));
    }
    else {
        forcecoul = 0.0;
    }
    if (rsq < cut_ljsq[itype][jtype]) {
        r6inv = r2inv * r2inv * r2inv;
        forcelj = r6inv * (lj1[itype][jtype] * r6inv - lj2[itype][jtype]);
    } else
        forcelj = 0.0;

    fforce = factor_coul * forcecoul + factor_lj * forcelj * r2inv;

    double eng = 0.0;
    if (rsq < cut_coulsq[itype][jtype]) {
        phicoul = force->qrd2e * qi * atom->q[j] * sqrt(r2inv) * (1.0 + (rf_fctr_1 / rf_fctr_2) *
(pow(sqrt(rsq)/cut_coul[itype][jtype],3.0)))
- force->qrd2e * qi * atom->q[j] * (1.0 / cut_coul[itype][jtype]) * (3.0 *
epsilon_rf[itype][jtype] / rf_fctr_2);
        eng += factor_coul * phicoul;
    }
    if (rsq < cut_ljsq[itype][jtype]) {
        philj = r6inv * (lj3[itype][jtype] * r6inv - lj4[itype][jtype]) - offset[itype][jtype];
        eng += factor_lj * philj;
    }

    return eng;
}

```

A.3 OBMD Architectural Document

In LAMMPS, a **fix** is a modular component that applies specific operations to a group of atoms during a simulation. Fixes are used to impose constraints, apply forces, modify atom properties, or perform other tasks at each timestep. The purpose of a fix in LAMMPS is to be flexible and extensible, allowing developers to add a custom functionality, and implement custom behavior by overriding relevant methods.

The `obmd` extension is implemented as a LAMMPS fix, enabling grand-canonical molecular dynamics simulations with special boundary conditions and external forces. It operates by:

- Managing particle insertion and deletion in buffer regions,
- Applying external forces to maintain user-defined boundary conditions,
- Communicating particle data across processors using MPI.

Key Components of the `obmd` Fix

1. **Fix Class:** The fix is implemented as a C++ class derived from the base `Fix` class. The base class provides a common interface and utility functions.
2. **Initialization:** Fixes are initialized during the setup phase of a simulation. This includes parsing input parameters, allocating memory, and preparing any data structures required for the fix.

A fix is defined in the input script using the `fix` command. For example:

```
fix                2 all obmd
```

This applies the `obmd` fix to all atoms.

3. **Interaction with LAMMPS MD Procedure:** Fixes are executed at specific points during the simulation. This fix overrides two key methods of the `Fix` base class to perform its operations, as specified with the `setmask()` function.
 - `pre_exchange()` : Handles particle insertion and deletion. This function is invoked before atoms are exchanged between processors. It:
 - Deletes particles that cross open boundaries.
 - Computes the number of particles to be inserted based on buffer conditions.
 - Inserts new particles into specified regions using the USHER or near algorithms.
 - Deletes particles that may overlap or violate boundary conditions.
 - `post_force()` : Applies external forces to atoms in specified regions. This function is called after force calculations in the MD timestep. It:
 - Computes momentum and shear forces based on user-defined parameters.
 - Distributes forces across atoms using weighting functions (e.g., smooth or step distributions).

MPI is used to distribute work across CPUs in a parallel simulation environment:

- **Particle Deletion:** The `try_deleting()` function identifies particles to be deleted based on their positions. MPI is used to:
 - Reduce deletion counts across processors.
 - Ensure consistent deletion of particles across the distributed domain.
- **Particle Insertion:** The `try_inserting()` function attempts to insert particles into specified regions. MPI is used to:
 - Broadcast insertion attempts and results.
 - Ensure particles are inserted without overlap across processors.
- **Force Distribution:** Functions like `reg_force()` and `reg_force_perp()` compute and apply forces to atoms. MPI is used to:
 - Sum forces across processors.

- Distribute forces proportionally to atom properties.

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References

Acronyms used

GPU	graphical processing unit
OBMD	open-boundary molecular dynamics
MD	molecular dynamics
PBCs	periodic boundary conditions
ROI	region of interest
rf	reaction field
DPD	dissipative particle dynamics
SPC	simple point charge
LJ	Lennard-Jones
EOS	equation of state
RDF	radial distribution function

Software mentioned

LAMMPS Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator
OBMD open-boundary molecular dynamics

URLs referenced

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Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/149>
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OBMD GitHub repository ... <https://github.com/chocolatesoup/OBMD-LAMMPS-extension/tree/main>

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